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SELF-MONITORING OF BLOOD GLUCOSE: EFFECTS ON ADHERENCE TO
LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION AMONG PREDIABETIC ADULTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Research indicates that diabetes mellitus (DM) has become a worldwide health problem, causing significant morbidity and mortality. Prediabetes is a major risk factor for developing Type 2 DM, with approximately 5%–10% of cases per year progressing to DM. This study was designed to determine whether home self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) encourages adherence to a lifestyle modification in an effort to decrease or delay the development of Type 2 DM.

An experimental design study was used, with random assignment of subjects to groups. Recruitment involved a convenience sampling of 40 primary care patients. Inclusion criteria included males or females, ages 40–75, and a fasting plasma sugar (FBS) between 100 and 125 mg/dL. Both groups received a lifestyle modification with the treatment group performing SMBG at home over 3 months. Outcomes of interest were self-efficacy, fasting blood sugar (FBS), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), weight, Body Mass Index (BMI), and lipid levels.

Paired and independent sample t tests were used to compare the differences within and between groups on all variables. Analysis of demographic and background variables were performed using Pearson's correlation, paired and independent sample t tests, and analysis of variance.

Results showed the treatment group with a significant increase in self-efficacy compared to the control group ($p < .008$) and from baseline to follow-up ($p = .000$). A significant weight loss and decrease in BMI and triglycerides was seen in both groups ($p < .05$) with a decrease in FBS in the combined group from baseline to follow-up ($p = .022$).

In prediabetics, SMBG increases self-efficacy, which has been shown to favorably affect health behaviors. An in-office, 20-minute lifestyle modification led to significant decreases in weight, BMI, FBS, and triglyceride levels.

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BACKGROUND

Diabetes mellitus (DM) has become an endemic worldwide health problem that is expected to reach pandemic proportions, thereby causing significant morbidity and mortality. In 2002 there were 76,813 reported deaths in the United States from diabetes, with only India and China surpassing these numbers at 156,235 and 125,510 deaths, respectively (Wolfram Research, Inc., 2014). According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC; 2011), the total prevalence of DM in this country is 25.8 million or 8.3% of the population. There were 1.9 million new cases of DM diagnosed in people over the age of 20 in 2010; an additional 79 million people were diagnosed with prediabetes, a condition known as hyperglycemia, where blood glucose levels are above normal but below the diagnostic criteria for diabetes.

The prevalence of DM is rising worldwide, and it is projected that by the year 2050, 25% to 28% of the U.S. adult population will have been diagnosed with this disease (Boyle, Thompson, Gregg, Barker, & Williamson, 2010). The prevalence of prediabetes is also rising; it is projected that 470 million people will have prediabetes by the year 2030, with approximately 5% to 10% per year progressing to DM (Tabak, Herder, Rathmann, Brunner, & Kivimaki, 2012). DM spares no gender or race, and it is estimated that approximately 13 million men and 12.6 million women in the United States over the age of 20 have this disease. National survey data from 2007–2009 show a prevalence of DM according to ethnicity: 11.8% of Hispanics, 12.6 % of non-Hispanic Blacks, 8.4% of Asian Americans, and 7.1% of non-Hispanic Whites have been diagnosed with DM (CDC, 2011).

DM is associated with significant morbidity and mortality. In the United States, it is the leading cause of kidney failure and of new cases of blindness among adults aged 20 to 74. Other complications of DM include heart disease, stroke, hypertension, neuropathies, peripheral vascular disease, and dental disease. Diabetics are more susceptible to infections and have worse prognoses after acquiring these illnesses (CDC, 2011).

It has been well documented that lifestyle modification can often prevent the development of Type 2 DM. The results of the Diabetes Prevention Program (DPP) demonstrated that lifestyle modification is a cost-effective strategy for preventing Type 2 DM in high risk adults (Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group [DPPRG], 2012b). In the study on lifestyle intervention and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT; the SLIM study), it was demonstrated that postprandial glucose metabolism and insulin resistance in subjects can be improved with a diet and exercise lifestyle intervention (Roumen et al., 2008). Because prediabetes is a significant risk factor for the development of Type 2 DM in adults, prevention strategies such as lifestyle modification and the variables that influence motivation to execute them should be investigated to decrease the risk among this high-risk group of population.

Problem Statement

DM, Type 2, is a chronic health illness with serious health consequences. It often compromises patients' quality of life and has a negative impact on family members and communities that must bear the caregiving responsibilities and financial burden of this disease. Its incidence and prevalence is on the rise, with estimates that by the year 2030, there will be 438 million adults worldwide with diabetes and 472 million

with prediabetes (Ramachandran & Snehalatha, 2011). The total prevalence of DM in the U.S. adult population is projected to increase from 14% in 2010 to 21% by the year 2050 (Boyle et al., 2010). According to the CDC (2011) the total cost associated with diabetes in the U.S. in 2007 was \$174 billion dollars, of which \$58 billion was due to disability, loss of work and premature mortality.

While lifestyle interventions have been shown to improve glycemic control, nonadherence to treatment regimens, especially when patients are asymptomatic, is a widespread problem and is of particular concern. Studies have shown poor adherence rates to lifestyle interventions, specifically diet and exercise. In a quantitative review of 50 years of research in published empirical studies, the range of average adherence rates have been cited to be from 4.6% to 100%, with a median of 76% and an overall average of 75.2% (DiMatteo, 2004). Lower adherence rates have been cited at approximately 50% to medication regimens and even lower for behaviorally oriented lifestyle interventions (Hayes, McDonald, & Garg, 2002).

Given the significant morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs associated with Type 2 DM, it behooves America as a society to implement strategies to prevent this burdensome disease. There has been much research to date on the implementation of lifestyle modification programs for high-risk adults to prevent the onset of Type 2 DM, but little is known about ways to enhance patient adherence to these programs. There is a need to examine various strategies to increase patient compliance to lifestyle modification programs for the prevention of Type 2 DM.

Objectives of the Project

The objectives of this project were to determine:

- Whether home self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) levels and lifestyle changes modify prediabetic adults' level of risk for developing Type 2 DM by improving their adherence to these changes, as measured by FBS and HbA1c.
- Whether home SMBG levels and lifestyle changes modify prediabetic adults' perceived level of self-efficacy in improving their lifestyle practices.

Clinical Question

Do adult prediabetic patients who self-monitor their blood glucose levels at home have improved and better adherence to lifestyle modification programs when compared to adult prediabetic patients who do not self-monitor, as measured by lower fasting blood glucose and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and improved self-efficacy?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The search strategy used in reviewing the literature was electronic databases including CINAHL, Medline, Pub Med, The Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar as well as reference lists from published articles and books. Search terms included *diabetes, prediabetes, adherence and compliance to lifestyle interventions, self-monitoring of blood glucose, diabetic diet, and self-efficacy*. Searches were worldwide, limited to the English language, and included articles published from 2002 to 2013. Websites used were the ADA and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (USFDA).

This literature review focuses on studies that both supported and refuted the benefit of using SMBG in the current management plan of insulin-dependent and noninsulin-treated Type 2 DM, with and without self-care interventions. In addition, the literature review examines current evidence-based studies on lifestyle intervention for prediabetics, Type 2 DM prevention, and factors influencing adherence to treatment regimens. There is a paucity of research in the use of SMBG as part of the therapeutic management of prediabetics for the prevention or delay of the onset of Type 2 DM and for its use in influencing adherence to prevention strategies such as lifestyle modifications.

Prevention or Delay of Onset of Type 2 DM

According to the ADA (2012), prediabetes is defined as impaired fasting glucose or a fasting plasma glucose between 100 and 125 mg/dl; IGT or an oral glucose tolerance test at 2 hours with a loading dose of 75g of between 140 and 199 mg/dl; or a HbA1c between 5.7 and 6.4%, repeated and confirmed on separate days. It has been well documented that patients with IFG and/or IGT, have a significantly increased risk

of developing diabetes and its comorbid conditions and complications (DPPRG, 2012a, National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases [NIDDK], 2008). In fact, elevated HbA1c levels are a strong predictor of progression to Type 2 DM. Efforts should therefore focus on targeting high-risk populations, with additional strategies needed to achieve aggressive glycemic control in prediabetics to prevent or delay the onset of Type 2 DM. The DPPRG (2002) has shown in its landmark study, the DPP, that there was a reduction in the incidence of Type 2 DM with a lifestyle modification program inclusive of diet and physical activity. A description of major systematic randomized prospective studies for primary prevention of Type 2 DM prepared by Ramachandran and Snehalatha (2011) demonstrated conclusively that the onset of Type 2 DM can be prevented or delayed by lifestyle modification and/or by the use of some medication regimens. However, lifestyle modification seems to achieve greater benefit, is more cost effective, and has a more favorable safety profile (Ramachandran & Snehalatha, 2011). Clinical guidelines from the American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists (AACE; 2011) call for prediabetics who are overweight or obese to modify their lifestyle to include weight loss and a physical activity regimen. They call for organized programs with appropriate follow-up so as to benefit from these efforts.

Adherence to Treatment Regimens

An important goal for the success of any medical treatment plan is to maximize patient adherence. A lack of adherence to medical therapies can be a source of great frustration to medical providers, who spend much time and effort in devising both pharmaceutical and nonpharmaceutical treatment plans for the intended well-being of their patients. Evidence-based studies may provide the rationale for an effective

therapeutic medical treatment regimen, but there can be no clinical effectiveness without patient adherence to the regimen. In a meta-analysis of 569 studies, the average percentage of adherence across studies was 75.2%. Adherence rates to health behavior and diet treatment plans were 69.7% and 59.3%, respectively (DiMatteo, 2004). There have been much published data on the variability of patient adherence to treatment regimens and the reasons contributing to it. Various theoretical models have been established that focus on the understanding and prediction of patients' adherence to medical recommendations, such as the health belief model, the theory of planned behavior, and the like (DiMatteo, 2004). Illness perceptions; perceived value of therapies; and a lack of symptoms, knowledge, and motivation are just some of the factors that have been implicated in the high rate of nonadherence to medical treatment therapies.

Many authors of published studies have recognized that adherence—specifically to lifestyle interventions—is a key component for successful implementation of medical treatments. In a study by Bonomo et al. (2010), it was found that an SMBG policy that included a 6-point glucose profile performed every 2 weeks was associated with a significant reduction in HbA1c, but only in compliant patients. The authors concluded that compliance was of paramount importance in achieving these results. In another study to determine the effect of a 3-year diet and exercise lifestyle intervention on glucose tolerance, insulin resistance, and metabolic cardiovascular risk factors in Dutch subjects with IGT, Roumen et al. (2008) concluded that lifestyle intervention did show a sustained beneficial effect on 2-hour glucose concentrations, insulin resistance, and

2-hour free fatty acids; however, the researchers added that for implementation, more research is needed about factors influencing adherence.

It is important for medical providers to recognize and implement different strategies that will encourage patient adherence to medical treatment recommendations, especially lifestyle modifications. One such strategy is to understand the value of motivation as a tool for enhancing adherence to medical therapies. According to a study on an SMBG-structured lifestyle program in noninsulin-treated Type 2 DM conducted by Kempf, Kruse, and Martin (2010), the authors concluded that “the evaluated SMBG structured lifestyle intervention is applicable to motivate individuals with Type 2 DM for lifestyle changes which will improve glucometabolic and general health” (p. 547).

Patient SMBG has long been a recognized and accepted integral component in diabetes management for patients to monitor, assess, and communicate to their healthcare providers the effectiveness of treatment regimens on glycemic control. The recommendations by the ADA for 2013 on SMBG are for its use in patients on insulin therapies. Self-monitoring of blood glucose has also been recognized as being helpful in guiding treatment decisions and for patient self-management in diabetics, as part of a broader educational lifestyle intervention in those on insulin and non-insulin therapies (ADA, 2013). Numerous studies have been published assessing the impact of SMBG on glycemic control in Type 2 DM with conflicting results. In an open, randomized, three-arm parallel group trial, Farmer et al. (2007) found no evidence that SMBG, with or without instruction in incorporating findings into self-care, improves glycemic control in noninsulin-treated Type 2 DM, with a patient mean age of 65.7 years. A similar result was found in a randomized control trial (RCT) comparing the effect of SMBG versus no

monitoring on glycemic control, body mass index (BMI), and hypoglycemia in newly diagnosed Type 2 diabetics; however, study subjects were all males (O’Kane, Bunting, Copeland, & Coates, 2008). In a systematic review of 30 RCTs and 36 observational and nonrandomized studies comparing SMBG with no SMBG, Clar, Barnard, Royle, and Waugh (2010) reported only 10 trials showing a statistically significant reduction in HbA1c of 0.21%. Although the authors admitted that many of the trials were of poor quality, they suggested that there was limited clinical effectiveness in improving glycemic control in Type 2 DM on oral agents or diet alone with SMBG monitoring. They further concluded that “SMBG may lead to improved glycemic control only in the context of appropriate education . . . in terms of lifestyle and treatment adjustment” (p. iii).

Alternatively, recent reviews of evidence have suggested improvement in glycemic control with SMBG. In a meta-analysis conducted by St John, Davis, Price, and Davis (2009) of 23 studies, including six RCTs, on the value of SMBG in noninsulin-treated Type 2 DM, it was shown that there was an SMBG-related reduction in HbA1c levels of 0.22 (95% CI, 0.34% to 0.11%). Showing similar results, Alleman, Houriet, Diem, and Stettler (2009) performed a meta-analysis and systematic review to assess the effect of SMBG on glycemic control in noninsulin-treated patients with Type 2 DM. Fifteen RCTs were included in the analysis that showed a beneficial effect of SMBG compared with non-SMBG, with reduction of HbA1c levels (-0.31%; 95% CI, -0.44% to -0.17%). Study findings did not show any significant changes in HbA1c levels with more frequent SMBG compared with less intensive SMBG.

The ROSSO-in-Praxi, a SMBG-structured 12-week lifestyle intervention in noninsulin-dependent Type 2 DM, was another study which showed a statistically significant reduction in blood glucose and HbA1c levels among participants. While it could be argued that the improved glycemic control could have been due to the structured lifestyle modification alone, a 2-year mean follow-up of this study demonstrated that those participants who continued daily SMBG had a total decrease in HbA1c of 0.3% compared to those who discontinued SMBG and had a HbA1c increase of 0.1% ($p = .05$). Weight loss was identified as a strong contributor to the decrease in HbA1c levels. The researchers suggested that “those persons who were able to identify the relationship between their nutrition/physical activity and their blood glucose levels and to use this knowledge to improve their lifestyle might benefit from daily SMBG in the long run” (Kempf et al., 2010, p. 63).

There has been only one published RCT assessing the impact of self-monitoring of blood glucose on the lifestyles of subjects with hyperglycemia. This study was conducted on 247 middle-aged male workers at the Matsushita Electric Industrial Co. at 38 local health service stations in the workplaces of the Matsushita Corporate Group, located in various parts of Japan. Diet advice and information on DM were provided to both the intervention and control group. Glucometers to test fasting blood sugars (FBSs) and pedometers to measure walking steps were given to the intervention group. Results showed no significant change in fasting plasma glucose level between the groups. A statistically significant increase in HbA1c levels and decreased BMI were seen in both groups with BMI reductions 3.6 times greater in the intervention group than in the control group. There was an increase in physical activity in the intervention group

and a significantly larger decrease in HbA1c levels from baseline to study end in a greater number of subjects in the intervention group as compared to the control group. The authors surmised that the SMBG and increased physical activity, as measured by pedometers, in the intervention group led to weight reduction by helping subjects make lifestyle changes. This weight loss may contribute to lowered HbA1c levels by having a beneficial effect on the prevention of Type 2 DM (Takata, Ou, Nishida, & Sakagami, 2002). This study cannot be generalized to other populations. In addition, because the intervention group received additional lifestyle training (i.e., pedometers) compared to the control group, the results of this study cannot be attributed to SMBG alone.

In the studies that show a benefit in SMBG as part of a lifestyle intervention program for improved glycemic control, a variety of reasons have been discussed and proposed. It has been posited that an increase in knowledge regarding the connection between nutrition and physical activity and blood glucose levels, reinforced by the performance of SMBG, may be responsible for better glycemic control (Kempf et al., 2010). Patients who test their blood glucose levels pre and post prandially may benefit from the immediate feedback of diet on their blood sugars (Takata et al., 2002). Some cite SMBG as a catalyst for self-empowerment in self-management skills in Type 2 DM (Clar et al., 2010), while others see SMBG as a motivational tool for patient adherence to medical treatment recommendations (Farmer et al., 2007).

As the incidence of Type 2 DM increases, primary care providers (PCPs) will take on a greater role in detecting high-risk populations and implementing prevention strategies that will include lifestyle modification programs to prevent or delay the onset of this widespread chronic health problem. One of the many challenges that medical

providers will face is that of patient adherence to medical recommendations for the prevention of this disease. While SMBG has been an accepted practice in the management of Type 2 DM, to date it has had no clinically accepted role as part of a lifestyle modification program in prediabetics. Patients with IFG have been a group of people who have been largely left to employ their own strategies to reduce their blood glucose levels through reducing weight, eating less carbohydrates (carbs), and exercising. It is only when these patients become diabetic that they are given more structured medical therapies including glucometers, diabetic diets, and monitoring for diabetic complications. Given that prediabetics have a significant risk of developing Type 2 DM and that microvascular complications can begin at this early stage of the disease continuum (Buysschaert & Bergman, 2011), it behooves the medical community to become aggressive in recommending structured lifestyle modification programs, within the context of self-management, to prediabetics in order to prevent and/or delay the progression to Type 2 DM. These programs should incorporate a variety of strategies to encourage patients' adherence to medical recommendations. In today's changing healthcare environment, patients will be taking on more self-management responsibilities for their chronic medical conditions and must be empowered to do so. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the role of SMBG in enhancing patients' adherence to a lifestyle modification for prediabetics to prevent or delay the onset of Type 2 DM. The aim was also to explore the role of SMBG in improving patients' perceived self-efficacy in managing their prediabetic state.

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

All research should be guided by a theoretical and conceptual framework. A theoretical framework looks at theories which help to guide and direct the research project while a conceptual framework identifies the tools and methods used to provide a focus for the research (Moran, Burson, & Conrad, 2014).

The theoretical framework that guided the research in this project was the health belief model, a psychological model that helps to predict health behaviors of individuals. It was developed in the 1950s by a group of social psychologists working at the U.S. Public Health Service to attempt to explain why there was a lack of participation in preventive disease programs (Rosentock, Strecher, & Becker, 1988). Its core assumptions are perceived susceptibility or one's perceived vulnerability in getting a disease; perceived severity or one's opinion of the severity of the consequences of that disease; perceived benefits or one's belief that the efficacy of the action is valued to reduce the risk of the disease; perceived barriers or one's opinion of the costs, tangible and psychological, of the intervention; cues to action or strategies to activate the readiness to follow the intervention; and the latest added concept to help the HBM integrate the challenges of changing unhealthy behaviors: self efficacy. This last concept is the confidence of one's ability in performing the action (Daddario, 2007).

According to Bandura's (1977) self-efficacy theory, a change in behavior is influenced by one's belief in one's capabilities in mastering the behavior. This concept is closely linked to the belief that the given behavior will lead to the expected outcome. In a review of studies of the concept of self-efficacy as it relates to health practices, it was found that "self-efficacy appears to be a consistent predictor of short- and long-term

success” and that there are “strong associations between self-efficacy and progress in health behavior change and maintenance” (Strecher, DeVellis, Becker, & Rosenstock, 1986, p. 87). Self-efficacy has been shown to affect adherence to treatment recommendations and plays a major role in the behavioral change process (Mishali, Omer, & Heymann, 2010). It has been suggested that cost prevention efforts should include addressing self-efficacy as an enhancing strategy toward preventing Type 2 DM (Serrano, Leiferman, & Dauber, 2007).

In this project, the identified population at risk, prediabetics, were targeted to receive educational information to heighten their perceived susceptibility of developing Type 2 DM. The participants were educated on the consequences of this disease as well as how to employ prevention strategies through lifestyle modification. Perceived barriers were addressed through reassurance and assistance of staff, and self-efficacy was promoted through training and guidance in performing the lifestyle modification and intervention.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study was an experimental design. This type of design is used to show a causal effect between an intervention that manipulates the independent variable and its effect on the dependent variable, or outcome of interest. Experimental designs are characterized by having an intervention, a control group that does not receive the intervention, and having random assignment of study subjects. This procedure involves assigning study subjects to different groups at random, with each participant having an equal chance of being in each group (Polit & Beck, 2012). In this project, the study subjects were randomly assigned to either an experimental or control group. This was done by a coin toss by the medical assistant because the principal investigator was blinded as to which participants received the intervention.

Cost-Benefit Analysis

Given the significant long-term cost savings of preventing the onset of Type 2 DM and after conducting a simple cost-benefit analysis of the project, it was concluded that this study was economically feasible. The main costs of the implementation of this project were for glucometer, test supplies, lancets, and disposable needle containers. Additional costs were for a pocket-sized carbohydrate reference book and educational handouts as tools to implement the lifestyle modification. The above costs per study participant were estimated to be approximately \$15.00, which did not include any monetary compensation for the researcher, assistants, or data analysis costs. Glucometers, test strips, lancets, a disposable Sharps container, and educational material were provided to all study participants at no charge from the supply kept at the medical

facility. There were no costs involved with participation in this study for any of the study participants.

Power Analysis

A power analysis was performed to determine detectable effect size given a sample size, setting power at .8 and alpha at .05. The difference in the changes of fasting blood glucose (in mg/dL) between the two groups was analyzed first. Based on previous research by Takata et al. (2002), the standard deviation of the changes in fasting blood glucose in each group was estimated to be 19.0. While the research by Takata et al. was not the same as that conducted for the present study, the results by these researchers were helpful in obtaining a rough estimate of standard deviation that was necessary in developing the power analysis. The graph in Figure 1 shows various effect sizes (Y-axis), assuming a standard deviation of 19.0, for different sample sizes (X-axis), using power of 0.8 and two-tailed significance level .05. Effect size here was the difference in changes of FBS between the control and treatment groups.

To see a difference of approximately 17.2 mg/dL in the changes of fasting blood glucose between the control and treatment groups, a sample size of $n = 20$ in each group is required. Increasing the sample sizes allows for the detection of smaller differences, but there are difficulties in obtaining more than 20 samples per group. This analysis can also be applied to the difference in changes of the HbA1c variable. Previous research by Takata et al. (2002) and Farmer et al. (2007) gave different estimates for the standard deviation of the changes in HbA1c percentage levels in the treatment and control groups. Takata et al. found 0.5; Farmer et al. found 1.0. The latter value of 1.0 was used as it required less estimation than in the value of Takata et al.

Figure 1. Independent two-sample *t* test: Fasting blood sugar (FBS). $SD = 19$; power = 0.8; two-tailed significance level = .05.

The graph in Figure 2 shows various effect sizes (Y-axis), assuming a standard deviation of 1.0 and sample sizes (X-axis) with a power of 0.8 and two-tailed significance level of .05. Effect size is the difference in changes of HbA1c levels between the control and treatment groups. Using the previously stated sample size of $n = 20$ in each group allowed for the detection of changes of sizes 0.91 percentage point in HbA1c and larger.

The change in fasting blood glucose from the baseline level to the follow-up level in each of the control and treatment groups was also analyzed. Using the previous estimate for standard deviation of change in fasting blood glucose (19.0) from Takata et

Figure 2. Independent two-sample t test: glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). $SD = 1.0$; power = 0.8; two-tailed significance level = .05.

al. (2002), the graph in Figure 3 shows the effect size (Y-axis) and sample size (X-axis) for power 0.8 and two-tailed significance level .05 is built. Effect size is the change in fasting blood glucose from the baseline level to the follow-up level (in mg/dL). Using a sample size of $n = 20$ allowed for changes of 12.5 mg/dL from the baseline to the follow-up fasting blood glucose levels in either the control or treatment group.

The change in HbA1c baseline and follow-up levels in the control and treatment groups was also analyzed. Using the previous estimate for standard deviation of change in HbA1c (1.0) from Farmer et al. (2007), the graph in Figure 4 shows the effect size (Y-axis) and sample size (X-axis) for power 0.8, and two-tailed significance level .05

Figure 3. Paired samples t test: Fasting blood sugar. $SD = 1.0$; power = 0.8; two-tailed significance level = .05.

Figure 4. Paired samples t test: Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). $SD = 1.0$; power = 0.8; two-tailed significance level = .05.

was built. Effect size is the change in the HbA1c baseline and follow-up levels (in percentage points). Using a sample size of $n = 20$ allowed for changes of approximately 0.66 percentage point in the baseline and follow-up fasting blood glucose levels in either the control or treatment group.

Recruitment and Inclusion-Exclusion of Study Participants

After receiving Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from California State University, Long Beach (CSULB), and requesting and obtaining permission from the medical facility (see Appendices A and B, respectively), study candidates were invited to participate in this study by convenience sampling of an accessible population of patients presenting to a private medical office for routine primary care services. Eligible candidates were invited to participate in the study by flyers (see Appendix C) that were directly mailed to eligible candidates receiving care at the medical facility of David M. Aron, MD, in Hacienda Heights, California. Flyers were also distributed in the exam rooms and waiting room of the medical facility for all patients to access. Given the practical constraints, a sample size of 40 participants were randomly assigned to both the experimental and control groups, satisfying the minimal sample size needed for this study. The sampling criteria marked characteristics of the target population for this study. Inclusion criteria were the following: males or females between the ages of 40 and 75 years of age and who had had a nationally accredited laboratory documenting fasting plasma glucose between 100 and 125 mg/dL within the last 3 months. Participants had to be able to read and understand English and capable of performing a blood glucose stick test at home after receiving instructions. Exclusion criteria applied to those who had ever been diagnosed with diabetes, were on any medication for the

prevention of diabetes, were currently taking or had taken oral or injectable steroids within the last month, who were unable to return to the office in 3 months, or who had any comorbid condition precluding the ability of the participant to adhere to a diet and exercise modification. Informed consent (see Appendix D) was obtained from all eligible participants.

The Setting

This project was conducted at a private outpatient medical office practice in an urban area of Los Angeles County, California. The facility has two primary care practitioners: one adult nurse practitioner and one internal medicine physician. The practice provides primary healthcare services to approximately 3,000 adult patients, ages 16 and older. Approximately 50% of the patients are enrolled in commercial health maintenance organizations (HMO) or Medicare Advantage plans. The remaining 50% are enrolled in Medicare, preferred provider organizations, or fee-for-service health plans. The patient population of this practice is heterogeneous, consisting of Caucasians, Hispanics, Asians, African Americans, and Middle Easterners. Patients are predominantly English speaking and are assigned to practitioners according to patient preference and practitioner availability. The practice was established in the community in 1981.

Study Protocol

Once a participant agreed to participate, he or she was asked to make an appointment with the principal investigator for two 30-minute office visits: one initial visit and one final office visit 3 months later. Participants in both groups were asked to fill out the demographics and self-efficacy questionnaires (see Appendices E and F,

respectively), upon consenting to participate. All participants received a 20-minute, one-on-one lifestyle modification program by the principal investigator with written educational material including a low-carb diet (under 100 grams of carbs a day for females; under 120 grams of carbs a day for males) reference book and label reading of food products, a handout explaining their risk for Type 2 DM and its complications and what they could do about it, and handouts addressing the physiology of eating and physical activity (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Lifestyle modification.

The principal investigator then left the room and the medical assistants randomly assigned subjects, by a coin toss, into two groups: control and experimental. All participants were instructed not to disclose to their PCP whether they had been assigned to the experimental or control group.

Participants in the experimental group received the home glucometer (intervention or independent variable) with test strips, lancets, and a Sharps container. Verbal instructions for use of glucometer for SMBG levels and for proper disposal of the

Sharps container were given by the medical assistants. The medical assistants had been trained to perform this instruction per routine office protocol. The principal investigator observed the two medical assistants' instructions and performances of SMBG.

According to Polit and Beck, (2012), interrater reliability concerns the agreement between two independent observers or coders on making simultaneous and independent observations. Instructions and sample glucose testing results were equivalent between both medical assistants, thus resulting in strong interrater reliability.

Participants were asked to demonstrate their understanding by exhibiting the proper technique using the control drops supplied with the glucometer. In addition to demonstrating ability to perform a glucose check correctly, this step also ensured that the glucometer and test strips were working together properly. Participants in the experimental group were asked to test and retest their blood sugars at home every 2 weeks; they were instructed to check their blood glucose immediately before and at 2 hours after eating their first meal of the day. The optimal frequency of SMBG is unknown, and testing recommendations should be individualized and will depend on many different factors. Although there are no current SMBG guidelines for prediabetics, most experts agree that multiple daily readings, especially fasting, preprandial (before meals), and 2 hours postprandial (after meals) are appropriate testing intervals for many diabetic patients (ADA, 2013a; Parkin & Davidson, 2009; Taylor & Campbell, 2007). Participants were further instructed to repeat the blood glucose self-test in the same manner over the next 3 months, for a total of 12 glucose readings. The glucose readings were automatically stored in the glucometer's memory. Participants in the control group continued to receive the standard care. Participants in the control group were wait listed

to receive the glucometer and Sharps container at the end of the 3-month study period and received the same instructions for use and Sharps container disposal at that time (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Self-monitoring of blood glucose intervention materials.

All participants in both the control and experimental groups, upon verbal agreement, received a scripted reminder phone call by the medical assistant (see Appendix G) every 2 weeks to encourage their participation in the study, with an additional reminder to those in the experimental group to perform their blood glucose testing.

At the final office visit, all participants filled out a final self-efficacy questionnaire. Medical assistants transposed all 12 glucometer readings from those in the experimental group onto the participant-matched serial number on the glucometer coding tool. At baseline and at the end of the 3-month study period, outcomes of interest, which included measurements of fasting plasma glucose, glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C), lipid panel, weight, BMI, and participants' self-efficacy questionnaires, were coded onto the participant-matched control number on the coding tool. All participants were individually debriefed at the end of their 3-month study period by the principal investigator.

Instruments

The following instruments were used in this study: (a) the Freestyle Lite® glucometer (see Appendix H); (b) biochemical serum markers (lipids, fasting plasma glucose, HbA1C) performed at a nationally accredited laboratory most utilized by the medical facility; (c) an eye-level balance beam scale with height rod that recorded height and weight (BMI calculated automatically from these measurements); (d) the participants' demographic form-coding tool used to identify baseline demographic data and other relevant data of interest, as well as to code biometric data (see Appendix I); (e) the self-efficacy questionnaire; and (f) educational material consisting of a calorie fat and carbohydrate counter pocket guide (see Appendix J). The lifestyle modification educational materials included written information on prediabetes, diabetes (see Appendix K), a low-carb diet (Appendix L), reading of nutrition facts of food products, physical activity, the physiology of eating (see Appendix M) and a summary of instructions on glucometer and lancet device use (see Appendix N). Instructions for proper disposal of Sharps container were also given to participants (see Appendix O). A description of each of these measures follows.

Blood Glucose Meters

Blood glucose meters are valid instruments used by the patient, outside the medical office, to test their blood glucose levels. The ADA (2008) has recommended SMBG as part of routine diabetes management. Blood glucose meters sold in the United States are reliable measures of patients' plasma glucose levels. All meters marketed in the United States must meet standards before the USFDA approves them for sale. The USFDA uses guidelines set by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO)

as follow: Ninety-five percent of meter test results must be within plus or minus 20% of the actual blood glucose level; for results below 75mg/dl, 95% of test results must be within plus or minus 15 points of the actual blood glucose level (Blood Glucose,” 2013).

There are a variety of different home blood glucose meters on the market. While most of them have similar functions, there are common features of these meters that may vary, such as blood sample size, data storage capacity, time of finger stick to test result, and so on. In this study the Freestyle Lite® glucometer, manufactured by Abbott Pharmaceutical, was used because this device is widely available, is covered by most insurers, and is utilized by the majority of diabetics at this medical facility. It allows use of one of the smallest blood samples (0.3µL) and has a 5-second time to result. In addition, it works at a minimum temperature of 40°F, has a memory capacity of 400 results, and requires no coding of test strips. A second application of blood may be applied to the test strip within 60 seconds if the first blood sample was insufficient—a feature well suited for people who are new to self-testing. The Freestyle Lite® also allows for alternate site testing besides the fingertips (i.e., hand, forearm, upper arm, thigh, or calf). It has two application sites on the test strip to facilitate ease of use among right- or left-handed individuals. There is no coding or calibration necessary for this device; however, a coding solution lasting 3 months is provided with the glucometer to ensure that the test strips and device are working together properly (Vo, Foepfel, & Flynn, 2011).

Serum Biomarkers

Physiologic serum biomarkers are used to detect and monitor many medical conditions. A fasting blood glucose and HbA1C (a 3-month average of blood glucose

levels expressed as a percentage) are blood tests commonly used to detect and monitor for diabetes and prediabetes. Lipid panels that include total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein (HDL) or the “good” cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) or the “bad” cholesterol, and triglyceride level are common measures of fat in the blood and are used as markers for coronary artery disease. For all diagnostic lab tests, the medical facility involved in this study utilizes a nationally accredited laboratory, in accordance with the recognized ISO quality management system, aimed at producing consistently valid results.

Height and Weight Scales

Scales are a valid measurement tool for height and weight. This medical facility utilizes an eye-level, balance beam medical scale with height rod. BMI is a standard calculation of height and weight to determine body fat. The formula for calculation is weight in pounds divided by height in inches multiplied by height in inches, multiplied by 703. Typically BMI is calculated by using a computer software-driven calculator. This medical facility’s electronic medical record automatically calculates the BMI from the input of the patient’s height and weight.

Demographics Form-Coding Tool

A participant’s demographics form and coding tool was developed by the principal investigator to collect demographic and other relevant data from participants to be used in the statistical analysis. The coding tool was developed to code biometric measures used in the statistical analysis of results. The following data were collected by the principal investigator for the reasons listed below:

Age. Age may affect the ability of the participant to implement the lifestyle modification. According to a cross-sectional survey design by Uchenna, Ijeoma, Pauline, and Sylvester (2010), it was found that factors such as age, gender, marital status, educational level, and occupation were all associated with adherence to dietary management in patients with diabetes. Also, older adults are at higher risk for developing diabetes.

Gender. There may be differences associated with gender on adherence to lifestyle modification (Uchenna et al., 2010).

Marital status. Marital status may affect adherence to the lifestyle modification and intervention due to influences of others on the participant (Uchenna et al., 2010).

Ethnicity. Prediabetes, self-efficacy, and adherence to lifestyle modification and intervention may vary among different ethnic groups. In a study by Serour, Alqhenaei, Al-Saqabi, and Mustafa (2007) on cultural factors and patients' adherence to lifestyle measures, the authors concluded that "cultural and demographic variables need to be considered to improve adherence to lifestyle measures" (p. 291).

Education level. Education levels may affect self-efficacy and the understanding and ability of the participant to adhere to the lifestyle modification and intervention (Uchenna et al., 2010).

Employment status. Employment status may affect adherence to lifestyle modification and intervention. Studies show that time constraints due to employment may affect lifestyle behaviors (Fitzgerald & Spaccarotella, 2009).

Participants were also asked to respond to the following item, "Do you or have you ever lived with someone who has diabetes?" Those living with diabetics may be

affected by the lifestyle behaviors, including diet, of the diabetic. In a study by Klomegah (2006), an important finding revealed that when people were around those who ate in a healthy manner to control their blood sugar, they, too, ate in a way that helped them control blood sugar.

Participants were asked to characterize their level of physical activity as inactive, low activity, medium activity, or high activity. According to the ADA's (2013) *Standards of Medical Care*, various studies have shown that physical activity has had a beneficial effect on glycemic control in diabetics and prediabetics. Lowered blood glucose levels can be seen up to 24 hours or more after physical activity due to the body becoming more sensitive to endogenous insulin levels

Finally, participants were asked if they had ever been told that they were prediabetic or had a higher than normal fasting blood sugar. Emotional adjustment reactions may affect coping abilities in newly diagnosed prediabetics and may interfere with educational interventions and affect glycemic control. In a study by Pibernik-Okanovic Roglic, Prasek, and Metelko (1996), on emotional reactions to newly detected diabetic patients, feelings of coping with the disease, negative emotional reactions, and weak coping abilities were seen in the initial struggle against the disease—all having an effect on long-term indicators of glycemic control.

In addition to the demographic data, a coding tool item was included and was used to maintain confidentiality; laboratory specimen numbers, rather than any identifiers, were used as the participants' control numbers and allowed for the matching of data to the respective participants' forms.

Coding tool, serial number of glucometer, and glucometer test results.

These were used to maintain confidentiality when transposing glucometer test results to the corresponding participant. Also, serial numbers of medical devices were important to record in case of manufacturer's recalls. Glucometer test results were a main interest of outcome in this study.

Coding tool, FBS, HbA1C (baseline and follow-up). These glycemic biomarkers were used to screen for and monitor prediabetics and diabetics. How the biomarkers were affected by diet and exercise was a main outcome of interest in this study.

Coding tool, weight, BMI (baseline and follow-up). Weight and BMI are risk factors for diabetes and are affected by diet and exercise. Changes in these measurements were an outcome of interest in this study.

Coding tool, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol (HDL-C), LDL cholesterol (LDL-C), triglycerides (baseline and follow-up). These are the standard and routine individual blood tests that comprise a lipid panel used as biomarkers for cardiovascular risk. Cholesterol and triglyceride levels are affected by diet and exercise and were an outcome of interest in this study.

Self-efficacy questionnaire. Self-efficacy questionnaires are commonly used in studies to measure an individual's perception of his or her ability to master a specific behavior or task. Self-efficacy impacts adherence to treatment regimens and has a role in diabetes education. Using a 7-item, 5-point Likert scale, participants' confidence in their ability to perform certain tasks or behaviors were measured using the Pre-Diabetic Self-Efficacy Scale (PDSS). This scale was adapted by the principle investigator from the

study by Serrano et al. (2007). According to the study by Serrano et al. (2007), the authors incorporated an adapted self-efficacy questionnaire from existing valid and reliable survey instruments into their Diabetes Risk Questionnaire. Variables included “diabetes prevention,” “eating healthy,” “eating habits,” “physical activity,” “weight control,” “risk reduction,” and “health promotion” (p. 127).

In the present study, the principal investigator adapted the items to fit prediabetics and to target specific practices. The following specifications were made in the items: Eating healthy was replaced by “low carbohydrate diet”; weight control, by “healthier weight,” “blood sugar monitoring,” “controlling blood sugar,” “prevent or delay the onset of diabetes,” “achieve a healthier lifestyle,” or “increase physical activity,” which were all appropriate variables to consider when adopting the lifestyle modification and/or intervention for prediabetics used in this study.

A second self-efficacy questionnaire was mailed to the participants at 2 weeks after the initial recruitment to calculate test-retest reliability of the tool. Test-retest reliability is “the assessment of the stability of an instrument by correlating the scores obtained on two administrations” (Polit & Beck, 2012, p. 744). Face validity was used to validate the operationalization of the prediabetic self-efficacy constructs. According to Polit and Beck (2012), face validity involves an instrument that measures what it looks like or purports to be measuring. Quality of face validity was improved by obtaining agreement from the medical facility’s practitioners that the constructs were good measures of prediabetic variables.

Low-Carbohydrate Diet

In general, a low-carb diet is one that restricts, to some degree, the consumption of foods that have a high percentage of caloric intake from carbs such as sweets, grains, beans, fruits, breads, rice, pastas, starchy vegetables, and alcohol. The ADA's (2008) *Clinical Practice Recommendations* support low-carb diets for weight management of people with diabetes for up to one year. Although there is no universal standard of how many carbs should be consumed in a daily diet or how many carbs per day constitute a low-carb diet, most sources report a low-carb diet as comprising from 30 grams to 130 grams of carbs per day (Hite, Berkowitz, & Berkowitz, 2011). In the present study, female participants were instructed to keep their total daily carb intake to no more than 100 grams per day and male patients were instructed to limit their daily carb intake to no more than 120 grams per day. All participants were instructed on how to read nutrition facts of food products. The principal investigator reviewed the physiology of eating and discussed the association of prediabetes and diabetes and its complications with each participant.

The CalorieKing® calorie, fat, and carbohydrate counter pocket guide is a national best selling reference text on nutrition data for food products with 24 annual editions to date. It was researched and compiled by Allan Borushek (2011), a biochemist and dietitian, and has won the National Health Information Award. It also contains a short diabetes guide section in association with the Joslin Diabetes Center.

Physical Activity

Physical activity is a part of most lifestyle modification programs for the benefit of promoting a healthier lifestyle. There are many published studies that incorporate

physical activity into treatment regimens for diabetics and for the prevention of diabetes (DPPRG, 2012a; Lauritzen, Borch-Johnsen, & Sandboek, 2007). Specific physical activity programs are best tailor made for each individual; however, any general increase in physical activity can have a beneficial effect as an adjunct to diet modifications. Participants in the present study were encouraged to increase their physical activity as appropriate and after checking with their healthcare provider, with the following suggestions: Take the stairs instead of the elevator; park the car at a further spot from their destination; take regular walks; work in the yard or garden; and/or take an exercise class.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data set for all demographic and background variables, biometric measures, and self-efficacy responses. Mean and standard deviation were used for numeric variables; frequency and frequency percentage were used for categorical variables.

Pearson's correlation was used to assess the test-retest reliability of the self-efficacy tool at baseline and at 2 weeks for 19 of the 40 study subjects. Independent two-sample *t* tests were used to compare the magnitude of the differences of fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels between control and treatment groups. This analysis was also used to compare the magnitude of the differences between control and treatment groups for self-efficacy and all other biometric variables.

Paired sample *t* tests were used to compare baseline and follow-up fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels within both control and treatment groups. This analysis was

also used to compare baseline and follow-up responses to self-efficacy questions and all other biometric data within both control and treatment groups.

Analysis of demographic and background variables in this study were performed using Pearson's correlation, paired sample t tests, independent two-sample t tests, and analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS

Characteristics of the Sample

A convenience sample of 40 subjects from an accessible population of patients presenting to a private medical office for routine primary care services and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were recruited into this study. Twenty-two subjects were randomly assigned to the control group; 18 were randomly assigned to the treatment group. For all variables $N = 40$, except for (a) baseline LDL-C, $N = 39$ due to one study subject having an incalculable LDL-C as a result of a triglyceride level in excess of 400 mg/dL; and (b) ethnicity, $N = 38$ as only the three most represented groups were analyzed. The total self-efficacy score was obtained by summing each of the seven individual self-efficacy responses.

Demographic Variables

Age ranges were 40 to 75 years, with a mean age in control and treatment groups of 60.7 and 61.1, respectively ($M = 60.7$, $SD = 8.3$; $M = 61.1$, $SD = 6.4$). There were 14 males (35%) and 26 females (65.0%) in this study. Gender differences were seen between the control and treatment groups with almost double the number of females in the control groups versus the treatment group, $n = 17$ (77.3%) vs. $n = 9$ (50%), and almost double the number of males in the treatment group versus the control group, $n = 9$ (50%) vs. $n = 5$ (22.7%). A typical study participant was either Caucasian or Hispanic and had education beyond high school. Half of the study subjects were employed either full-time or part-time; the other half were retired, unable to work, or looking for work. These demographic variables were comparable between the control and treatment groups

except for a higher number of control group subjects having less than some college education (see Table 1).

Background Variables

Most study subjects, $n = 26$ (65%), indicated that they presently do not live or had ever lived with anyone who has had diabetes. This factor was comparable between control, $n = 12$ (54.5%), and treatment groups, $n = 14$ (77.8%). Most study subjects reported performing either low or medium physical activity, and this factor was comparable between control, $n = 18$ (81.9%), and treatment groups, $n = 17$ (94.4%). Most study subjects had been previously told that they were prediabetic, $n = 29$ (72.5%); this factor was also comparable between control, $n = 15$ (68.2%) and treatment groups, $n = 14$ (77.8%); see Table 1.

Biometric Variables at Baseline and Follow-Up

Table 2 shows baseline and follow-up serum levels for all biometric variables: FBS, HbA1c, weight, BMI, cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C, and triglycerides. The control group ($n = 22$) showed higher baseline and follow-up serum levels for FBS, HbA1c, weight, BMI, cholesterol, HDL-C, and LDL-C than the treatment group. Baseline and follow-up triglyceride levels were, however, higher in the treatment group.

Test–Retest Reliability

The test–retest reliability of the self-efficacy tool was assessed using the correlation coefficient between the baseline and retest survey scores (see Figure 7). The first 19 study subjects beginning the study were selected to be retested on the self-efficacy questions at 2 weeks after baseline. The baseline and retest responses to the seven self-efficacy questions were summed to create two sets of total self-efficacy

Table 1

Demographic and Background Variables for Study Participants (N = 40)

Variable	Total		Control ^a		Treatment ^b	
	<i>F</i>	%	<i>F</i>	%	<i>F</i>	%
Gender						
Males	14	35.0	5.0	22.7	9.0	50.0
Females	26	65.0	17.0	77.3	9.0	50.0
Marital status						
Married, domestic partner	31	77.5	14.0	63.6	17.0	94.4
Single (never married)	1	2.5	1.0	4.5	0.0	0.0
Divorced, separated	4	10.0	3.0	13.6	1.0	5.6
Widowed	4	10.0	4.0	18.2	0.0	0.0
Ethnicity						
Caucasian	16	40.0	9.0	40.9	7.0	38.9
Hispanic	16	40.0	9.0	40.9	7.0	38.9
African American	1	2.5	1.0	4.5	0.0	0.0
Asian	6	15.0	3.0	13.6	3.0	16.7
Prefer not to answer	1	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	5.6
Education						
Up to eighth grade	1	2.5	1.0	4.5	0.0	0.0
High school graduate or GED	8	20.0	6.0	27.3	2.0	11.1
Some college	17	42.5	10.0	45.5	7.0	38.9
Trade school	2	5.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	11.1
Bachelor's degree	7	17.5	3.0	13.6	4.0	22.2
Master's degree or higher	5	12.5	2.0	9.1	3.0	16.7
Employment						
Employed part-time	3	7.5	1.0	4.5	2.0	11.1
Employed full-time	17	42.5	10.0	45.5	7.0	38.9
Looking for work	2	5.0	2.0	9.1	0.0	0.0
Retired	15	37.5	7.0	31.8	8.0	44.4
Unable to work	3	7.5	2.0	9.1	1.0	5.6

(continued)

Table 1

Variable	Total		Control ^a		Treatment ^b	
	<i>F</i>	%	<i>F</i>	%	<i>F</i>	%
Ever lived with anyone with diabetes						
Yes	14	35.0	10.0	45.5	4.0	22.2
No	26	65.0	12.0	54.5	14.0	77.8
Physical activity level						
Inactive	3	7.5	3.0	13.6	0.0	0.0
Low	18	45.0	10.0	45.5	8.0	44.4
Medium	17	42.5	8.0	36.4	9.0	50.0
High	2	5.0	1.0	4.5	1.0	5.6
Diagnosed as prediabetic						
Yes	29	72.5	15.0	68.2	14.0	77.8
No	11	27.5	7.0	31.8	4.0	22.2

Note. GED = General Equivalency Diploma. For the variable of age, the mean and standard deviation, respectively, for total participants were 60.9 and 7.4; for the control group, 60.7 and 8.3; and for the treatment group, 61.1 and 6.4.

^a*n* = 22. ^b*n* = 18.

Table 2

Biometric Variables at Baseline and Follow-Up for Study Participants (N = 40)

Variable	Total		Control ^a		Treatment ^b	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Fasting blood sugar						
Baseline	108.28	7.37	110.45	8.02	105.61	5.61
Follow-up	104.85	10.69	106.82	9.81	102.44	11.50
HbA1c						
Baseline	5.99	0.25	6.03	0.23	5.92	0.28
Follow-up	5.99	0.29	6.05	0.31	5.91	0.26
Weight						
Baseline	190.65	55.72	199.05	63.72	180.39	43.63
Follow-up	183.90	56.16	192.32	65.42	173.61	41.79
Body Mass Index						
Baseline	30.78	7.24	33.01	6.12	28.05	4.93
Follow-up	29.65	7.25	31.84	8.32	26.96	4.60
Cholesterol						
Baseline	185.35	37.26	189.68	35.69	180.06	39.46
Follow-up	181.40	33.61	184.36	29.53	177.78	38.59
HDL-C						
Baseline	53.40	16.52	56.45	19.63	49.67	11.10
Follow-up	54.02	14.09	54.86	14.50	52.98	13.91
LDL-C						
Baseline	105.69	30.47	108.45	31.16	102.12	30.11
Follow-up	103.78	30.04	108.32	28.45	99.71	32.13
Triglycerides						
Baseline	147.70	77.29	136.55	51.49	161.33	100.36
Follow-up	114.15	48.79	106.09	32.27	124.00	63.16

Note. HDL-C = high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C = low-density lipoprotein cholesterol.

^a $n = 22$. ^b $n = 18$. scores. The resulting correlation coefficient between the aggregate baseline and retest self-efficacy scores was 0.632, a value that suggests that there was adequate reliability of the tool.

		Retest
Baseline	Pearson correlation	.632
	Significance (two-tailed)	.004
	<i>N</i>	19

Figure 7. Pearson's correlation for test–retest reliability. Bolding indicates correlation significance at the .01 level (two-tailed).

Self-Efficacy Responses at Baseline and Follow-Up

Table 3 shows comparable total self-efficacy scores at baseline between the control group ($M = 27.00$, $SD = 6.21$) and the treatment group ($M = 27.44$, $SD = 5.20$). Participants in both groups showed an increase in all self-efficacy questions except for questions 2, 3 and 4 (confidence in achieving a healthier weight and confidence in monitoring and controlling blood sugar).

Changes in Self-Efficacy Scores From Baseline to Follow-up Between Control and Treatment Groups

The means and standard deviations of the total and individual self-efficacy responses for the control and treatment groups were calculated. The baseline, follow-up, and change in score were all compared. The control group showed increases in all variables except for question 3, which showed a decrease, and question 4, which showed no change. The treatment group showed increases in all variables, with the size of the changes being much larger when compared to the control group. *t* tests were used to formally test these differences. Table 4 shows the results of independent samples *t* tests

Table 3

Self-Efficacy Variables at Baseline and Follow-Up (N = 40)

Variable	Total		Control ^a		Treatment ^b	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
Total						
Baseline	27.20	5.71	27.00	6.21	27.44	5.20
Follow-up	29.73	5.58	27.55	6.44	32.39	2.57
Self-efficacy 1						
Baseline	3.55	0.99	3.59	0.96	3.50	1.04
Follow-up	4.08	1.02	3.73	1.17	4.50	0.62
Self-efficacy 2						
Baseline	3.93	0.76	3.86	0.77	4.00	0.77
Follow-up	4.23	0.95	3.86	1.04	4.67	0.59
Self-efficacy 3						
Baseline	4.13	0.97	4.09	1.07	4.17	0.86
Follow-up	4.27	0.99	3.86	1.08	4.78	0.55
Self-efficacy 4						
Baseline	3.85	0.95	3.86	0.89	3.83	1.04
Follow-up	4.18	0.87	3.86	0.99	4.56	0.51
Self-efficacy 5						
Baseline	3.85	1.03	3.73	1.16	4.00	0.84
Follow-up	4.25	0.90	4.00	1.02	4.56	0.62
Self-efficacy 6						
Baseline	3.90	1.11	3.91	1.15	3.89	1.08
Follow-up	4.48	0.85	4.23	1.02	4.78	0.43
Self-efficacy 7						
Baseline	4.00	1.06	3.95	1.09	4.06	1.06
Follow-up	4.25	1.10	4.00	1.16	4.56	0.98

^a*n* = 22. ^b*n* = 18.

Table 4

Independent Samples Test for Self-Efficacy and Other Biometric Variables

<i>t</i> test for equality of means (equal variances assumed)							
Variable ^a	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Mean difference	<i>SE</i> difference	95% CI of difference	
						Lower	Upper
Self-efficacy							
d-Total	-2.803	38	.008	-4.39899	1.56924	- 7.57575	- 1.22223
d-SE1	-2.696	38	.010	- .86364	.32028	- 1.51201	- .21526
d-SE2	-2.444	38	.019	- .66667	.27282	- 1.21895	- .11438
d-SE3	-2.210	38	.033	- .83838	.37936	- .60636	- .07040
d-SE4	-2.416	38	.021	- .72222	.29890	- 1.32732	- .11712
d-SE5	- .881	38	.384	- .28283	.32118	- .93303	- .36737
d-SE6	-1.783	38	.083	- .57071	.32011	- 1.21875	.07733
d-SE7	-1.572	38	.124	- .45455	.28916	- 1.03991	.13082
Other biometric variables							
d-Weight	0.200	38	.984	.05051	2.47340	- 4.95662	5.05763
d-BMI	- .214	38	.832	- .08581	.40181	- .89923	.72761
d-Chol	- .430	38	.670	-3.04040	7.07715	-17.36735	11.28654
d-HDL-C	-1.356	38	.183	-4.90202	3.61613	-12.22249	2.41845
d-LDL-C	.364	37	.718	2.27540	6.24832	-10.38489	14.93569
d-Trig	.331	38	.742	6.87879	20.77278	-35.772.78	-48.93108

Note. Two-tailed significance. CI = confidence interval.

^ad = difference; SE = self-efficacy; ; BMI = Body Mass Index; Chol = cholesterol; HDL-C = high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C = low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; Trig = triglycerides.

comparing the magnitude of changes in self-efficacy scores between the control and treatment groups. There was a statistically significant difference in the size of changes in total self-efficacy scores, $t(38) = -2.80, p < .05$, leading to the conclusion that those in the

treatment group saw greater increases in their total self-efficacy scores than those in the control group. The tests also showed statistically significant differences with questions 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 (see Appendix F). Questions 5 and 7 did not show statistically significant differences.

Changes in Self-Efficacy Scores From Baseline to Follow-up in Control and Treatment Groups

The results of paired *t* tests for the control group, comparing the baseline and follow-up self-efficacy responses, showed no statistical significance in all of the eight self-efficacy questions, $p > .05$, leading to the conclusion that there was no change in self-efficacy scores within the control group. The results of paired *t* tests for the treatment group, comparing the baseline and follow-up self-efficacy responses, showed statistical significance in all of the eight self-efficacy questions, $p < .05$, leading to the conclusion that there was a significant increase in self-efficacy scores within the treatment group. Participants in the control group did not improve any of their self-efficacy scores, while the treatment group subjects improved all of their self-efficacy scores (see Table 5).

Changes in FBS Levels Between Control and Treatment Groups

The magnitude of changes in blood glucose levels between the control and treatment groups were compared. Patients in the control group had an average baseline FBS level of 110.45 mg/dL and an average follow-up FBS level of 106.82 mg/dL, yielding an average decrease of -3.64 mg/dL. Patients in the treatment group had an average baseline FBS level of 105.61 mg/dL and an average follow-up level of 102.44, yielding an average decrease of - 3.17 mg/dL. The independent samples *t* test was applied to compare whether there was a significant difference in changes in fasting blood

Table 5

Paired Samples Test for Self-Efficacy: Treatment Group

Variable	Paired differences			95% CI of difference		<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>SEM</i>	Lower	Upper			
Total: BL-FU	-4.944	4.151	.978	-7.009	-2.880	-5.053	17	.000
SE1: BL-FU	-1.000	1.029	.243	-1.512	-.488	-4.123	17	.001
SE2: BL-FU	-.667	.686	.162	-1.008	-.326	-4.123	17	.001
SE3: BL-FU	-.611	1.092	.257	-1.154	-.068	-2.374	17	.030
SE4: BL-FU	-.722	1.018	.240	-1.228	-.216	-3.010	17	.008
SE5: BL-FU	-.556	.616	.145	-.862	-.249	-3.828	17	.001
SE6: BL-FU	-.889	.963	.227	-1.368	-.410	-3.915	17	.001
SE7: BL-FU	-.500	.857	.202	-.926	-.074	-2.474	17	.001

Note. Significance is two-tailed. SE = self-efficacy; CI = confidence interval; BL-FU = baseline to follow-up.

glucose between the two groups. The *t* test was not statistically significant, $t(38) = -0.16$, $p > .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that there were no statistically significant changes in FBS levels in the control or treatment groups from baseline to follow-up. Notably, there was a statistically significant decrease in FBS in comparing baseline to follow-up levels in the combined group, $t(39) = 2.39$, $p = .022$.

Changes in FBS Levels From Baseline to Follow-Up in Control and Treatment Groups

The paired samples t test was applied to the control and treatment groups to test whether there was a statistically significant change between baseline and follow-up FBS levels. The paired t test was not statistically significant in the control group, $t(21) = 1.75, p > .05$; or in the treatment group, $t(17) = 1.59, p > .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that there were no statistically significant changes in FBS levels in the control or treatment groups from baseline to follow-up.

Changes in HgbA1c Levels Between Control and Treatment Groups

The magnitude of changes in HbA1c levels between the control and treatment groups were compared using the independent t test. Patients in the control group had an average baseline HbA1c level of 6.032% and an average follow-up level of 6.050%, yielding an average increase of 0.018%. Patients in the treatment group had an average baseline HbA1c level of 5.928% and an average follow-up level of 5.911%, yielding an average decrease of -0.017%. The independent samples t test was applied to compare whether there is a statistically significant difference in changes in HbA1c between the two groups. While the treatment group showed a minimal decrease in HbA1c level compared to the minimal increase in HbA1c level in the control group, this was not statistically significant, $t(38) = 0.556, p > .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that there was no statistically significant difference in the magnitude of HbA1c percentage changes between the control and treatment groups (see Table 6).

Table 6

Paired Samples Test for Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1c): Control and Treatment Groups

Variable	Paired differences					<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>SEM</i>	95% CI of difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Control: HbA1C								
BL to FU	-.01818	.22601	.04819	-.11839	.08203	-.377	21	.710
Treatment: HbA1C								
BL to FU	.01667	.15435	.03638	-.06009	.09342	.458	17	.653

Note. Significance is two-tailed. HbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; BL = baseline; FU = follow-up.

Changes in HbA1c Levels From Baseline to Follow-Up in Control and Treatment Groups

The paired samples *t* test was applied to the control and treatment groups to test whether there was a statistically significant change between baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels. The paired *t* test was not statistically significant in the control group, $t(21) = -.038, p > .05$; or in the treatment group, $t(17) = 0.46, p > .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that there were no statistically significant changes in HbA1c levels in the control or treatment groups from baseline to follow-up.

Changes in Other Biometric Variables From Baseline to Follow-Up Between Control and Treatment Groups

The mean and standard deviations of the other biometric measures (weight, BMI, cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides) for the control and

treatment groups were calculated. The baseline, follow-up, and difference in measures were all compared. Both groups showed decreases in weight, BMI, cholesterol, LDL-C, and triglycerides. The control group showed larger decreases in BMI and cholesterol; the treatment group showed larger decreases in weight, LDL-C, and triglycerides. The control group showed a decrease in HDL-C; the treatment group showed an increase. The results of independent samples *t* tests were analyzed, comparing the magnitude of changes in biometric variables between the control and treatment groups. None of the tests showed statistically significant differences between the two groups, $p > .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that there was no statistically significant difference in the size of weight, BMI, cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglyceride changes between the control and treatment groups.

Changes in Other Biometric Variables From Baseline to Follow-Up in Control and Treatment Groups

The results of paired *t* tests for the control group, comparing baseline and follow-up biometric measures of weight, BMI and lipids, were analyzed. *t* tests showed statistically significant changes in weight, $t(21) = 4.53, p < .05$; BMI, $t(21) = 4.68, p < .05$; and triglycerides, $t(21) = 3.21, p < .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that the control group showed statistically significant decreases in weight, BMI, and triglycerides (see Table 7). The tests for cholesterol, $t(21) = 1.03, p > .05$; HDL-C, $t(21) = 0.53, p > .05$; and LDL-C, $t(21) = 0.03, p > .05$, were not statistically significant, thus leading to the conclusion that there was no statistically significant change in cholesterol, HDL-C, and LDL-C within the control group.

Table 7

Paired Sample Test for Other Biometric Variables for Control and Treatment Groups

Variable	Paired differences						<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>SEM</i>	95% CI of difference					
				Lower	Upper				
Control group									
Weight: BL-FU	6.72727	6.96373	1.48467	3.63973	9.81482	4.531	21	.000	
BMI: BL-FU	1.17136	1.17434	.25037	.65069	1.69204	4.679	21	.000	
Chol: BL-FU	5.31818	24.31223	5.18338	- 5.18338	16.09762	1.026	21	.317	
HDL-C: BL-FU	1.59091	14.14099	3.01487	- 4.67885	7.86067	.528	21	.603	
LDL-C: BL-FU	.13636	22.22032	4.73739	- 9.98830	9.98830	.029	21	.977	
Trig: BL-FU	30.45455	44.44336	9.47536	10.74946	50.15963	3.214	21	.004	
Treatment group									
Weight: BL-FU	6.77778	8.68776	2.04772	2.45746	11.09810	3.310	17	.004	
BMI: BL-FU	1.08556	1.36720	.32225	.40566	1.76545	3.369	17	.004	
Chol: BL-FU	2.27778	19.44768	4.58386	- 7.39333	11.94888	.497	17	.626	
HDL-C: BL-FU	- 3.31111	6.50799	1.53395	- 6.54746	- .07476	-2.159	17	.045	
LDL-C: BL-FU	2.41176	14.75660	3.57900	- 5.17538	9.99891	.674	16	.510	
Trig: BL-FU	37.33333	84.31523	19.87329	- 4.59565	79.26231	1.79	17	.078	

Note. Significance is two-tailed. BL-FU = baseline to follow-up; BMI = Body Mass Index; Chol = cholesterol; HDL-C = high-density lipid protein cholesterol; LDL-C = low-density lipid protein cholesterol; trig = triglycerides.

The results of paired *t* tests for the treatment group, comparing baseline and follow-up biometric measures of weight, BMI and lipids, were analyzed. *t* tests showed statistically significant changes in weight, $t(17) = 3.31, p < .05$; BMI, $t(17) = 3.37, p <$

.05; HDL-C, $t(17) = -2.16, p < .05$; and triglycerides, $t(17) = 1.88, p < .05$, leading to the conclusion that the treatment group had statistically significant decreases in weight, BMI, and triglycerides and an increase in HDL-C. The tests for cholesterol, $t(17) = 0.50, p > .05$; and LDL-C, $t(16) = 0.67, p > .05$, were not statistically significant, thus leading to the conclusion that there was no statistically significant change in cholesterol and LDL-C within the treatment group (see Table 7).

Data Analysis on Demographic and Background Variables

Age

A correlation analysis was used to analyze whether age had any relationship with the variables in the dataset. Figure 8 shows the correlations between age and change in weight and age and change in BMI. There was a statistically significant association between age and the two variables. Older participants tended to show smaller changes in weight or BMI compared to younger participants.

		d-Weight	d-BMI
Age	Pearson correlation	.354	.376
	Significance (two-tailed)	.025	.017
	<i>N</i>	40	40

Figure 8. Pearson's correlations for age. Bolding indicates correlation significance at the .05 level (two-tailed). d = difference; BMI = Body Mass Index.

Gender

Males and females were compared on all variables. Females showed a greater decrease in BMI (-1.49 lbs.) when compared to males (-0.47 lb.). The independent

samples *t* test showed that this difference was statistically significant, $t(38) = 2.67, p < .05$, thus leading to the conclusion that females had a greater BMI loss than males. Females also showed a greater decrease in weight; however, although this difference trended toward statistical significance, under strict adherence to alpha, it was not statistically significant, $t(38) = 2.00, p = .054$.

Baseline and follow-up FBS, HbA1c, weight, lipids, and total self-efficacy scores for males were compared. Males showed a FBS decrease of 4.43 mg/dL and a total self-efficacy score increase of 3.14 points. Paired samples *t* tests showed that these changes were not statistically significant, $t(13) = 1.84, t(13) = -2.09, p > .05$, although self-efficacy scores trended toward statistical significance, $t(13) = -2.09, p = 0.57$. Paired *t* tests for weight, BMI, FBS, triglycerides, and total self-efficacy scores for females were calculated. Females showed a decrease of 8.46 pounds, a decrease in BMI of 1.49, a decrease in triglycerides of 45.85, and an increase in total self-efficacy score of 2.19. Paired samples *t* tests showed that all of these changes were statistically significant, $t(25) = 7.90, t(25) = 7.93, t(25) = 3.43, t(25) = -2.12, p < .05$. Only males showed a statistically significant decrease in FBS; only females showed a statistically significant decrease in weight, BMI, triglycerides, and self-efficacy.

Education

Participants who indicated that they had completed only high school or less were compared on all variables with those who had some education beyond high school. Nine participants in the dataset indicated that they had no education beyond high school compared to 31 participants who indicated that they had at least some postsecondary education. Those with education more than high school showed a decrease of -0.04% in

HbA1c; those with a high school education or less showed an increase of 0.13%. The independent samples *t* test showed that this difference was statistically significant, $t(38) = -2.42, p < .05$. Participants completing more than high school also showed a decrease in cholesterol of 7.84 compared to an increase of 9.44 for participants with high school or less. The *t* test showed that this difference was statistically significant, $t(38) = -2.17, p < .05$. The *t* test also showed a statistically significant difference in total self-efficacy score between the two groups, $t(38) = 2.46, p < .05$, with the more-than-high school education group increasing in total self-efficacy score and the high school education-or-less group decreasing in total self-efficacy score (see Table 8).

Table 8

Summary Statistics: Education of Study Participants (N = 40)

Variable ^a	High school or less		More than high school	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
HbA1c				
Baseline	6.10	0.25	5.95	0.25
Follow-up	6.23	0.24	5.92	0.27
d-HbA1c	0.13	0.13	- 0.04	0.20
Cholesterol				
Baseline	177.78	28.77	187.55	39.52
Follow-up	187.22	25.39	179.71	35.83
d-Cholesterol	9.44	24.75	- 7.84	19.96
Total self-efficacy				
Baseline	27.67	5.45	27.06	5.86
Follow-up	26.56	6.13	30.65	5.16
d-Total self-efficacy	- 1.11	3.92	3.58	5.30

^aHbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; d = difference.

Employment

Participants who indicated that they worked were compared on all variables with those who indicated that they did not work (see Table 9). Working participants showed a greater decrease in BMI than nonworking participants, $t(38) = 2.07, p < .05$, which was statistically significant according to the independent *t*-samples test. Baseline and follow-up variables were compared for the working and nonworking groups. The working participants showed a statistically significant decrease in weight, BMI, and triglycerides with a statistically significant increase in self-efficacy, $t(19) = 7.50, t(19) = 7.77, t(19) = 2.15, t(19) = 2.26, p < .05$, respectively. The nonworking participants showed a statistically significant decrease in FBS, weight, BMI, and triglycerides, $t(19) = 2.75, t(19) = 2.28, t(19) = 3.20, p < .05$, respectively; see Table 9.

Live or Lived With Someone With Diabetes

Participants who indicated that they lived with or had ever lived with someone with diabetes were compared on all variables with those who indicated that they did not or never lived with a diabetic). *t* tests showed no statistical significance between the groups. Those who lived or had ever lived with a diabetic showed a statistically significant decrease in weight and BMI, $t(13) = 2.79, t(13) = 2.95, p < .05$, respectively. The group who did not live or had never lived with a diabetic showed a significant decrease in weight, BMI, and triglycerides and a significant increase in HDL-C, and self-efficacy, $t(25) = 4.87, t(25) = 4.97, t(25) = 3.06, t(25) = -2.22, t(25) = -2.35, p < .05$, respectively; see Table 10.

Table 9

Summary of Statistics: Employment of Study Participants (N = 40)

Variable ^c	Working ^a		Not working ^b	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Fasting blood sugar				
Baseline	108.05	7.65	108.50	7.27
Follow-up	106.50	9.57	103.20	11.72
d-Fasting blood sugar	- 1.55	9.34	- 5.30	8.62
HbA1c				
Baseline	6.04	0.22	5.93	0.28
Follow-up	6.00	0.30	5.97	0.29
d-HbA1c	- 0.03	0.23	0.04	0.16
Weight				
Baseline	171.50	33.96	209.80	66.68
Follow-up	162.65	34.50	205.15	65.83
d-Weight	- 8.85	5.27	- 4.65	9.17
Body Mass Index				
Baseline	28.61	5.16	32.95	8.42
Follow-up	27.08	5.06	32.21	8.27
d-Body Mass Index	- 1.52	0.88	- 0.74	1.45
Cholesterol				
Baseline	199.10	35.32	171.60	34.70
Follow-up	191.55	28.04	171.25	36.27
d-Cholesterol	1.83	8.54	- 0.60	13.98
HDL cholesterol				
Baseline	55.55	15.56	51.25	17.56
Follow-up	57.38	12.77	50.65	14.84
d-HDL cholesterol	1.83	8.54	- 0.60	13.98

(continued)

Table 9

Variable ^c	Working ^a		Not working ^b	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
LDL cholesterol				
Baseline	117.00	15.56	51.25	17.56
Follow-up	111.10	28.19	96.45	30.74
d-LDL cholesterol	- 3.89	17.69	1.50	20.51
Triglycerides				
Baseline	154.50	97.43	140.90	51.69
Follow-up	114.05	51.67	114.25	47.08
d-Triglycerides	- 40.45	84.14	- 26.65	37.27
Total self-efficacy				
Baseline	29.35	4.04	25.05	6.39
Follow-up	31.60	3.86	27.85	6.46
d-Total self-efficacy	2.25	4.46	2.80	6.23

^a*n* = 20. ^b*n* = 20. ^cHbA1c = glycated hemoglobin; d = difference; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; LDL = low-density lipoprotein.

Table 10

Summary Statistics: Participants Who Lived With or Had Ever Lived With a Diabetic (N = 40)

Variable ^c	Lived with diabetic ^a		Never lived with diabetic ^b	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Fasting blood sugar				
Baseline	111.14	8.65	106.73	6.22
Follow-up	105.57	14.18	104.46	8.56
d-Fasting blood sugar	- 5.57	10.14	- 2.27	8.42
HbA1c				
Baseline	5.96	0.22	6.00	0.27
Follow-up	5.93	0.32	6.02	0.28
d-HbA1c	- 0.04	0.22	0.02	0.18
Weight				
Baseline	195.64	69.44	187.96	48.10
Follow-up	189.07	72.90	181.12	46.20
d-Weight	- 6.57	8.83	- 6.85	7.18
Body Mass Index				
Baseline	31.14	9.23	30.58	6.11
Follow-up	30.00	9.64	29.46	5.79
d-Body Mass Index	- 1.14	1.45	- 1.13	1.16
Cholesterol				
Baseline	187.43	39.93	184.23	36.51
Follow-up	184.14	30.42	179.92	35.70
d-Cholesterol	- 3.29	24.98	- 4.31	20.80
HDL cholesterol				
Baseline	56.93	20.97	51.50	13.65
Follow-up	53.19	11.49	54.46	15.50
d-HDL cholesterol	- 3.74	16.61	2.96	6.81

(continued)

Table 10

Variable ^c	Lived with diabetic ^a		Never lived with diabetic ^b	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
LDL cholesterol				
Baseline	112.38	34.88	102.35	74.73
Follow-up	108.14	49.65	117.38	49.00
d-LDL cholesterol	- 0.69	22.63	- 1.35	17.61
Triglycerides				
Baseline	138.14	83.84	152.85	74.73
Follow-up	108.14	49.65	117.38	49.00
d-Triglycerides	- 30.00	76.13	- 35.46	59.06
Total self-efficacy				
Baseline	26.21	5.12	27.73	6.04
Follow-up	28.57	6.90	30.35	4.77
d-Total self-efficacy	2.36	4.91	2.62	5.67

^a $n = 14$. ^b $n = 26$. ^cHbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; d = difference; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; LDL = low-density lipoprotein.

Physical Activity

Participants who indicated that they were inactive or performed low physical activity were compared on all measures with those who indicated that they performed medium or high physical activity. There was no statistical significance between the groups. Paired t tests for those who were inactive or performed low physical activity showed a statistically significant decrease in weight, BMI, and triglycerides, $t(20) = 6.40$, $t(20) = 6.55$, $t(20) = 2.41$, $p < .05$, respectively. Paired t tests for those who indicated

medium or high physical activity showed a statistically significant decrease in weight, BMI, and triglycerides and a significant increase in self-efficacy, $t(18) = 2.17$, $t(18) = 2.38$, $t(18) = 2.41$, $t(18) = 2.17$, $t(18) = -2.42$, $p < .05$, respectively; see Table 11.

Previously Prediabetic

Participants who had been told in the past that they were prediabetic were compared with those who had never been told that they were prediabetic. There were no statistical differences between the two groups. Paired t tests showed a statistically significant decrease in FBS, weight, BMI, and triglycerides and an increase in self-efficacy among those who had been previously told that they were prediabetic, $t(28) = 2.20$, $t(28) = 3.91$, $t(28) = 4.05$, $t(28) = 2.52$, $t(28) = 3.22$, $p < .05$, respectively. Paired t tests in the group who were never known to be prediabetic showed a statistically significant decrease in FBS, weight, BMI, and triglycerides, $t(19) = 2.75$, $t(19) = 2.27$, $t(19) = 2.28$, $t(19) = 3.20$, $p < .05$, respectively; see Table 12).

Ethnicity

The results of ANOVA tests comparing Caucasians, Hispanics, and Asians showed no statistical significance difference in any of the measures (see Tables 13 and 14). Paired t tests for Caucasians in the sample showed a statistically significant decrease in weight and BMI, $t(15) = 3.42$, $t(15) = 3.54$, $p < .05$, respectively. Paired t -test results for Hispanics showed a statistically significant result in weight, BMI, and triglycerides, $t(15) = 3.58$, $t(15) = 3.85$, $t(15) = 2.18$, $p < .05$, respectively. Paired t tests for Asians did not show statistical significance for any measure.

Table 11

Summary Statistics: Physical Activity Level of Study Participants (N = 40)

Variable ^a	Inactive-low physical activity (<i>n</i> = 21)		Medium-high physical activity (<i>n</i> = 19)	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
Fasting blood sugar				
Baseline	109.95	7.72	106.42	6.68
Follow-up	106.71	12.43	102.79	8.21
d-Fasting blood sugar	- 3.24	10.62	- 3.63	7.28
HbA1c				
Baseline	6.06	0.26	5.91	0.23
Follow-up	6.02	0.32	5.95	0.27
d-HbA1c	- 0.04	0.21	0.05	0.17
Weight				
Baseline	191.33	47.34	189.89	65.08
Follow-up	182.90	47.77	185.00	65.55
d-Weight	- 1.45	1.02	- 0.78	1.40
Body Mass Index				
Baseline	31.83	5.92	29.62	8.48
Follow-up	30.37	5.90	28.84	8.59
d-Body Mass Index	- 1.45	1.02	- 0.78	1.40
Cholesterol				
Baseline	184.24	31.46	186.58	43.65
Follow-up	181.14	28.76	181.68	39.10
d-Cholesterol	- 3.10	18.92	- 4.89	25.54
HDL cholesterol				
Baseline	49.95	12.56	57.21	19.67
Follow-up	53.27	12.36	54.84	16.08
d-HDL cholesterol	3.31	7.55	- 2.37	14.33

(continued)

Table 11

Variable ^a	Inactive-low physical activity (<i>n</i> = 21)		Medium-high physical activity (<i>n</i> = 19)	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
LDL cholesterol				
Baseline	106.85	27.57	104.47	33.98
Follow-up	102.29	26.27	105.42	34.40
d-LDL cholesterol	- 3.10	16.28	0.95	21.99
Triglycerides				
Baseline	155.33	72.66	139.26	83.27
Follow-up	120.38	48.40	107.26	49.60
d-Triglycerides	- 34.95	66.55	- 32.00	64.18
Total self-efficacy				
Baseline	27.00	5.39	27.42	6.19
Follow-up	29.14	4.64	30.37	6.54
d-Total self-efficacy	2.14	5.49	2.95	5.32

^aHbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; d = difference; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; LDL = low-density lipoprotein.

Table 12

Summary Statistics: Study Participants Previously Diagnosed as Prediabetic (N = 40)

Variable ^c	Prediabetic ^a		Not prediabetic ^b	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
Fasting blood sugar				
Baseline	110.10	7.68	103.45	3.39
Follow-up	106.00	12.06	101.82	4.96
d-Fasting blood sugar	- 4.10	10.03	- 1.64	5.87
HbA1c				
Baseline	5.96	0.26	6.06	0.24
Follow-up	5.96	0.32	6.06	0.20
d-HbA1c	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.19
Weight				
Baseline	193.10	60.68	184.18	41.65
Follow-up	187.00	60.92	175.73	42.54
d-Weight	- 6.10	8.41	- 8.45	5.26
Body Mass Index				
Baseline	30.93	8.17	30.38	4.12
Follow-up	29.92	8.18	28.93	4.10
d-Body Mass Index	- 1.01	1.35	- 1.45	0.91
Cholesterol				
Baseline	183.31	37.06	190.73	39.05
Follow-up	180.17	31.78	184.64	39.52
d-Cholesterol	- 3.14	23.87	- 6.09	17.05
HDL cholesterol				
Baseline	55.17	17.28	48.73	13.97
Follow-up	55.19	13.22	50.91	16.43
d-HDL cholesterol	- 0.02	13.17	2.18	5.13

(continued)

Table 12

Variable ^c	Prediabetic ^a		Not prediabetic ^b	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
LDL cholesterol				
Baseline	104.79	30.18	108.00	32.57
Follow-up	102.03	28.44	108.36	34.97
d-LDL cholesterol	- 1.71	20.41	0.36	16.18
Triglycerides				
Baseline	138.48	73.66	172.00	84.91
Follow-up	109.07	50.88	127.55	41.99
d-Triglycerides	- 29.41	62.75	- 44.45	71.24
Total self-efficacy				
Baseline	26.10	5.59	30.09	5.20
Follow-up	29.45	5.67	30.45	5.56
d-Total self-efficacy	3.34	5.59	0.36	4.15

^a*n* = 29. ^b*n* = 11. ^cHbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; d = difference; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; LDL = low-density lipoprotein.

Table 13

Summary Statistics: Ethnicity of Study Participants

Variable	Caucasian (n = 16)		Hispanic (n = 16)		Asian (n = 6)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
FBS						
Baseline	108.81	7.92	107.25	6.97	108.17	6.49
Follow-up	103.81	13.14	104.75	9.98	107.17	6.55
d-FBS	- 5.00	10.07	- 2.50	9.55	- 1.00	6.46
HbA1c						
Baseline	5.96	0.31	6.06	0.23	5.90	0.15
Follow-up	5.97	0.31	6.01	0.32	5.98	0.25
d-HbA1c	0.01	0.17	- 0.04	0.22	0.08	0.19
Weight						
Baseline	215.94	54.10	185.31	57.35	146.17	18.89
Follow-up	209.56	56.37	177.25	57.39	142.67	15.90
d-Weight	- 6.38	7.46	- 8.06	9.01	- 3.50	4.76
Body Mass Index						
Baseline	31.85	7.67	31.93	7.72	25.36	2.01
Follow-up	30.87	7.93	30.48	7.69	24.79	1.78
d-Body Mass Index	- 0.98	1.11	- 1.44	1.50	- 0.57	0.87
Cholesterol						
Baseline	173.44	33.37	186.75	31.43	210.50	34.67
Follow-up	167.44	33.29	189.06	24.95	202.83	36.76
d-Cholesterol	- 6.00	21.99	2.31	21.86	- 7.67	16.19
HDL-C						
Baseline	53.44	15.95	51.12	16.87	55.67	15.97
Follow-up	53.04	16.20	52.62	9.02	58.17	19.34
d-HDL-C	- 0.04	7.85	1.50	15.98	2.50	6.89

(continued)

Table 13

Variable	Caucasian (<i>n</i> = 16)		Hispanic (<i>n</i> = 16)		Asian (<i>n</i> = 6)	
	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>
LDL-C						
Baseline	94.00	24.54	113.40	32.19	116.17	24.33
Follow-up	91.44	27.69	112.25	26.83	120.00	33.90
d-LDL-C	- 2.56	18.92	1.47	19.06	3.83	13.91
Triglycerides						
Baseline	131.44	50.28	153.25	85.49	192.67	112.87
Follow-up	112.88	54.95	113.31	46.74	123.50	51.34
d-Triglycerides	- 18.56	51.14	- 39.94	73.31	- 69.17	74.38
Total self-efficacy						
Baseline	25.81	7.31	28.69	2.73	28.00	5.29
Follow-up	28.94	7.61	30.44	3.95	30.33	4.13
d-Total self-efficacy	3.12	6.81	1.75	3.75	2.33	4.55

Note. *n* = 38 because statistical analysis was conducted for the three major ethnic groups represented; one subject was African America, and another preferred not to specify ethnicity. FBS = fasting blood sugar; d = difference. HDL-C = high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C = low-density lipoprotein cholesterol.

Table 14

Analysis of Variance for Ethnicity of Participants (Caucasian, Hispanic, and Asian)

Variable	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
d-FBS					
Between groups	88.211	2	44.105	.498	.612
Within groups	3,100.000	35	88.571		
Total	3,188.211	37			
d-HbA1c					
Between groups	.075	2	.037		
Within groups	1.405	35	.040		
Total	1.480	37			
d-Weight					
Between groups	92.655	2	46.327	.749	.480
Within groups	2,166.187	35	61.891		
Total	2,258.842	37			
d-BMI					
Between groups	3.802	2	1.901	1.190	.316
Within groups	55.910	35	1.597		
Total	59.712	37			
d-Cholesterol					
Between groups	724.098	2	362.049	.805	.455
Within groups	15,734.771	35	449.565		
Total	16,458.868	37			
d-HDL cholesterol					
Between groups	48.093	2	24.046	.169	.846
Within groups	4,992.300	35	142.637		
Total	5,040.393	37			
d-LCD cholesterol					
Between groups	225.063	2	112.532	.335	.718
Within groups	11,422.504	34	335.956		
Total	11,647.568	36			

(continued)

Table 14

Variable	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
d-Triglycerides					
Between groups	11,705.686	2	5,852.843	1.389	.263
Within groups	147,503.708	35	4,214.392		
Total	159,209.395	37			
d-Self-efficacy					
Between groups	15.180	2	7.590	.263	.770
Within groups	1,010.083	35	28.860		
Total	1,025.263	37			

Note. d = difference; HbA1C = glycated hemoglobin; FBS = fasting blood sugar; BMI = Body Mass Index; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; LDL = low-density lipoprotein.

DISCUSSION

This randomly assigned, experimental design pilot study was used to determine whether SMBG encouraged adherence to diet and exercise (lifestyle modification) in prediabetics, in order to prevent or delay the onset of Type 2 DM. The statistically significant finding of this study was an increase in total self-efficacy scores in the treatment group as compared to the control group. There was also a statistically significant increase in all eight self-efficacy scores within the treatment group from baseline to follow-up, as compared to no statistically significant change in the control group. This result highlights the potential benefit of using novel strategies to improve patient self-efficacy with the goal of enhancing patient adherence to treatment regimens. According to Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, self-efficacy is one's perceived, not actual capabilities, which can influence behavior with strong associations seen between self-efficacy and positive health behavior change (Stretcher et al., 1986). One of the biggest challenges in preventing and controlling Type 2 DM is patient adherence to diet or lifestyle modification that, when followed, has had proven outcomes of success on glycemic control (DPPRG, 2012). If SMBG can effect an increase in self-efficacy, then there may be tremendous value in incorporating this tool as part of self-management for all prediabetics and diabetics.

Results failed to demonstrate a statistically significant reduction in FBS or HbA1c in those patients monitoring their blood glucose at home over a 3-month period of time. Previous studies on SMBG in improving glycemic control in Type 2 DM have shown mixed results. While the present study was one of the few studies conducted on prediabetics, the results found were similar to some other studies done involving Type 2

diabetics (Farmer et al., 2007; O’Kane et al., 2008). Although not statistically significant, patients in the treatment group had a minimal decrease in HbA1c percentage (-0.017%), compared to a minimal increase in the control group (0.018%). This lack of statistical significance may be due to the small sample size in this study or due to the narrow window of time of 3 months in measuring HbA1c from baseline to follow-up.

A key strategy for preventing Type 2 DM involves weight control. The Diabetes Prevention Study and the Diabetes Prevention Program trial have shown that a lifestyle intervention program in patients with IGT can prevent the onset of Type 2 DM by 58% (Ramachandran & Snehalatha, 2011). The Nurses’ Health Study concluded that BMI is a major predictor of the development of Type 2 DM (Koenigsberg, Bartlett, & Cramer, 2004). In the current study, both control and treatment groups showed statistically significant decreases in weight and BMI from baseline to follow-up; however, no statistically significant differences were seen between the groups, thereby leading to the conclusion that all study patients experiencing weight loss did follow the lifestyle modification given to them and that it proved effective. Additionally, patients’ FBS showed a decrease between baseline and follow-up when analyzed for the combined group.

Thirty-three out of the 40 study patients sustained a weight loss over 3 months. The mean weight loss in both groups approximated 7 pounds, with some patients losing up to 15 pounds. Interestingly, out of the seven patients who did not lose weight, five were in the control group.

Other biometric variables studied as secondary outcomes of interest were lipid levels. Both study groups showed statistically significant decreases in triglycerides,

with only the treatment group showing a statistically significant increase in HDL-C from baseline to follow-up. There were no statistically significant differences between the groups. Triglyceride levels more than cholesterol levels are sensitive to dietary changes, and one would expect a precipitous drop in these levels commensurate with the weight loss seen in both groups. The increase in HDL-C in the treatment group alone may be attributed to the unequal distribution of physical activity levels at baseline. The fact that the treatment group had almost twice the number of males than the control group and had reported an overall slightly higher physical activity level than the control group may account for this difference due to a known association between increased HDL-C and physical activity levels (Kodama et al., 2007).

Analyses was done on demographic and background variables with discussion of statistically significant and relevant findings only. A statistically significant association was found between age and change in weight and BMI from baseline to follow-up, with older participants showing smaller changes in these variables compared to younger participants. This association strengthens the need for early identification of prediabetics so that lifestyle changes can be implemented at the earliest possible time with the aim of maximizing the chances for a successful weight loss.

Education also has a statistically significant association with biometric and self-efficacy variables. Those completing more than high school had statistically significant improvements of HbA1c and cholesterol, with an increase in self-efficacy scores from baseline to follow-up. This finding may have been due to dietary differences, ability to comprehend, and self-confidence issues between the groups, for which more research is needed.

It is well recognized that exercise can lead to decreases in weight and BMI. There was a statistically significant decrease in weight, BMI, and triglycerides in both the inactive-to-low and the medium-to-high physical activity groups, with an additional decrease in FBS and an increase in self-efficacy in the latter group. This study's lifestyle modification included both a structured diet and a less structured exercise component. Study results supported the recommendation by the American College of Sports Medicine for greater amounts of physical activity to achieve weight loss and prevent weight regain in adults (Donnelly et al., 2009). It also supports the recommendation by the 2013 American Diabetic Association for diabetic adults to perform moderate to intense aerobic physical activity at least 3 days a week for improved glycemic control ,

Patients who had been previously told that they were prediabetic had a statistically significant increase in self-efficacy compared to those who had never been told. Because emotional adjustment reactions to newly diagnosed prediabetics may interfere with coping abilities (Pibernik-Okanovic et al., 1996), it seems understandable that self-efficacy would increase as the patient has a chance, over time, to adjust to this diagnosis. This factor is important for the clinician to recognize because many patients are not informed of mildly elevated blood glucose levels or are told that they are prediabetic until their blood glucose levels approach a diabetic range.

In an ANOVA of the three most represented ethnic groups in this study (i.e., Caucasian, Hispanic, and Asian), there were no statistically significant differences on all variables between these groups. However, there was a statistically significant decrease in weight and BMI in the Caucasian and Hispanic groups and a statistically significant decrease in triglycerides in the Hispanic group only. The Asian group showed no

statistical significance on any of the variables analyzed. There was an unequal distribution of Asians in this study compared to Caucasians and Hispanics, which could explain these results. Also, this study's lifestyle intervention was not tailored to cultural food preferences among ethnicities and did not explore baseline eating habits among the different ethnic groups.

Limitations of the Study

A significant limitation of this study was its small sample size that resulted in low statistical power. Although a power analysis was done to control for Type II errors, the results indicated that the difference in the size of the change of both FBS and HbA1c needed for an effect was significantly more than what would be considered clinically relevant.

Another limitation was that this study used convenience sampling to enroll subjects. This method of sampling is a weaker means of subject selection than random sampling, as the former fails to control for selection bias and leads to preexisting inequalities between groups.

Intervention fidelity may have been violated, as there was some variability in the time frame when patients returned to the office for their 3-month follow-up visit. Although patients in the treatment group were instructed to perform SMBG in the fasting state and subsequently 2 hours later, there was self-reported variability in this protocol. Although interrater reliability was performed by observing both medical assistants delivering the intervention with matched glucometer test results, the actual delivery of the intervention may have been inconsistent.

The weight loss seen in both groups may have been due to a Hawthorne effect, because consenting to be in this study could have affected the patient's motivation to adhere to the lifestyle modification. Finally, this study cannot be generalized to broader populations as it was specific to prediabetics who were between the ages 40 and 75 years old, in an urban private practice.

Implications for Clinical Practice

DM is a growing, widespread national health concern due to its deleterious effects on patient morbidity and mortality rates and patients' quality of life. Identifying populations at risk for this burdensome disease is a key strategy toward preventing or delaying its onset. Prediabetics are at greatest risk for developing Type 2 DM; therefore, efforts should be focused toward early detection so that preventive measures can be immediately implemented. Clinicians should therefore aggressively screen patients who are at risk for prediabetes not only with an FBS but also with the newly accepted standardized HbA1c test.

Healthy People 2020 (HealthyPeople.gov, 2013) is a leading health indicator with the national goal of improving health for all Americans by the year 2020. One of its objectives is to increase prevention behaviors in prediabetics who are at risk for diabetes. Analyses of this study's results highlighted the key role that the primary care, advanced practice nurse has in promoting healthy behaviors that positively affect health outcomes. Self-efficacy has a strong association with positive changes in health behavior; therefore, it behooves the nurse practitioner to find ways to increase patients' self-efficacy so that patients may successfully adhere to lifestyle changes. A statistically significant increase

in self-efficacy was seen in the treatment group in this study compared to the control group, where SMBG was the intervention used to encourage adherence to lifestyle modification. This finding alone may justify the use of SMBG as part of a lifestyle modification program. Other studies in the literature review have suggested the effective use of SMBG as an adjunct to diabetes management to improve glycemic control. While this study did not show a statistically significant improvement in HbA1c levels, presumably due to a small sample size, it did show that the treatment group had a minimal decrease in HbA1c levels and could have clinical relevance. Other clinical strategies for increasing self-efficacy are communicating all hyperglycemic test results to the patient, as study results show improvement in self-efficacy scores in patients who have been previously told that they were prediabetic.

Obesity and its association with prediabetes, diabetes, and other health problems have reached epidemic proportions. Clinicians are often frustrated with patients' lack of adherence to lifestyle changes. A striking result of this study indicated that both control and treatment groups had statistically significant decreases in weight, BMI, and triglyceride levels, with combined group showing a decrease in FBS, from baseline to follow-up after a 20-minute, in-office lifestyle modification by the nurse practitioner. In some cases, weight loss was in excess of 15 pounds over the 3-month study period. Younger patients showed a statistically significant greater change in weight, thus reinforcing the need for early implementation of lifestyle changes. This finding has enormous implications for encouraging clinicians to spend time in teaching lifestyle modifications to their patients and recognizing the value of this time spent. The present study's lifestyle modification included diet, exercise, and an awareness of the physiology

of eating as it pertains to Type 2 DM. Increasing patients' knowledge of their disease and how to improve their health may arguably lead to patient empowerment. More research is needed in this area to determine the effects of patient empowerment on adherence to medical treatments. Advanced practice nurses need to be aware of insurance reimbursements for health promotion services and should petition for adequate reimbursement rates for providing counseling to patients in need of lifestyle changes.

Higher education levels showed statistically significant improvements in HbA1c, cholesterol levels, and self-efficacy scores from baseline to follow-up. An ANOVA of ethnicities also showed statistically significant differences among variables within groups from baseline to follow-up. Clinicians need to tailor their lifestyle modification programs to patients' level of education and cultural eating patterns for the best possible result.

Conclusion

Health promotion, preventive health care services, and early detection of disease are the pillars of primary health care in this country. Patients who are prediabetic may benefit from early detection and implementation of lifestyle modifications that encourage weight loss and promote better health. SMBG is one strategy that has been successfully used in increasing self-efficacy scores in these patients. Self-efficacy has a strong association with positive changes in health behavior and may lead to clinically relevant improvement in glycemic control. Larger RCTs over a longer period of time are needed to prove a statistically significant effect. Future research is needed on additional cost-effective strategies or tools that may also increase self-efficacy and motivate patients to adhere to lifestyle changes. Significant weight loss has been shown in

prediabetics with as little as a 20-minute individualized lifestyle modification given by the clinician. This supports patient counseling as an important treatment plan for prediabetics in achieving a healthier weight. Additional research is needed to see whether this weight loss is sustainable over longer periods of time.

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APPENDIX A**LETTER REQUESTING PERMISSION TO DO STUDY**

David M. Aron, MD
3180 S. Colima Rd., Suite A
Hacienda Heights, Ca 91745

Dear Dr. Aron,

3-29-2013

I am planning to conduct a study to meet my Doctoral Project requirements in the graduate program at California State University at Long Beach through the L.A. Consortium Doctorate of Nursing Practice program. This study is entitled, Does Home Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose Encourage Adherence to Diet and Exercise in Pre-diabetic Adults as a Secondary Prevention for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus?

I plan to study a minimum of 60 patients over the time period from 6/01/2013 - 6/01/2014. The purpose of this study is to determine whether home self-monitoring of blood glucose levels will encourage pre-diabetic adults to actively participate in their care, resulting in greater adherence to lifestyle modification and a reduction of blood glucose levels in an effort to decrease the development of Type 2 diabetes mellitus and its associated medical, psychological and financial burdens to the patient, family community and society.

The selection procedure will be one of convenience sampling of patients meeting the inclusion criteria who have come to the office for a routine medical visit. I will also advertise the study, with your permission, through a flyer placed in the waiting room area of your office (see attached).

A fifteen-minute lifestyle modification program (diet, exercise, and informational educational materials) for the purpose of improving pre-diabetic patient's blood sugar levels and preventing the development of Type 2 diabetes mellitus will be given by me, and individually to all eligible participants. Participants will be randomly assigned to one of two groups, the experimental group or the control group by the toss of a coin by your medical assistant, which I will be blinded to. The experimental group will be given a Freestyle Lite© glucometer with test strips and lancets (intervention) with detailed instructions on how to test their blood glucose by the medical assistant as per your office protocol and with your permission. They will also be given a plastic Sharps container, which the patient will be instructed to use to properly dispose of the used lancets. Instructions will also be given for the proper disposal of the Sharps containers. Participants will be asked to test their blood glucose once before and once two hours after the first meal of their day every two weeks for three months for a total of 12 tests. A medical assistant, with your permission, will place a total of six phone calls over the three-month study period, to each participant at the number they provide, for the purpose of encouraging adherence to the lifestyle modification and if applicable, as a reminder to perform their blood glucose tests. The participant may opt not to receive

these phone messages. At the end of the study, the control group will receive the same intervention as the experimental group. I will conduct two individualized office visits, one initial and one three-month follow-up as part of the patient's routine medical follow-up as per your office protocols and to implement the study. I will personally retrieve only pertinent lab data and vital sign measurements from the electronic medical record and transpose this data to the coding tool on the patient questionnaire form.

In order to protect human subjects, I have obtained a signed informed consent from the patients who voluntarily wish to participate in this study. The patient demographics form has been designed with sensitivity. The Pre-Diabetic Self Efficacy Questionnaire used was adapted from a Diabetes Risk Self-Efficacy Questionnaire by Serrano et al. (2007) and has good reliability and validity. I will maintain strict confidentiality. No names will be on the patient questionnaire or survey tool, and specimen data will be transposed on a coding tool section on the bottom of the demographics form. No data as a result of this study will be added to the patient's electronic medical record. I will properly store the research data in a locked safe inside your facility, to which only you and I and my faculty advisor, Ahlam Jadalla, RN, MSN, PhD, will have access. I will properly destroy, by shredding, the records after a three-year time period. All participants, regardless of group will receive usual care as per your office protocol with regards to the lifestyle modification program.

There will be no additional expense to you or your facility, other than the time requested of your medical assistants to place reminder calls to patients, instruct patients on glucometer testing, and recording glucometer test results on the coding tool. I will be providing all the material and supplies necessary for the implementation of the intervention and lifestyle modification program. There will be no additional expense or remuneration to the participants in this study. Any participant may withdraw from this study at any time, without prejudice, and will still receive the intervention and lifestyle modification program.

I am writing to request your permission to conduct my study in your office.

Sincerely,

Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP

APPENDIX B
AGENCY APPROVAL LETTER

Internal Medicine
General Practice

626
(818) 968-0547
(213) 691-2454

DAVID M. ARON, M.D., F.A.C.M.

Diplomat, American Board of Internal Medicine
3180 Colima Rd.
~~10010 Hacienda Blvd., Suite 101 A~~
Hacienda Heights, CA 91745

To: Barbara Barlow Aron

Re: Permission to conduct a research study at my facility

Dear Barbara,

4-10-2013

This letter is in response to your request to perform research at my office as a requirement for the completion of your doctoral project and Doctorate of Nursing Practice degree from the L.A. Consortium. The study I am referring to is, does home self-monitoring of blood glucose encourage adherence to diet and exercise in pre-diabetic adults as a secondary prevention for type 2 Diabetes Mellitus?

I have reviewed your doctoral project proposal, consent to participate in research form, patient questionnaire/coding tool, self-efficacy questionnaire and educational materials to be used in the collection of data from our patients for your research study at my medical facility. I felt that your study was well thought out, particularly with respect to patient's rights, minimizing risks to the patient and confidentiality issues. I am happy to make myself and my staff available to you, in any way that is helpful to you, for your study.

Please keep me informed as to when you will be starting your data collection and I will wholeheartedly support you in performing this research at my medical facility.

Sincerely,

David M. Aron, M.D.

APPENDIX C**RECRUITMENT FLYER****STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE ADHERENCE TO LIFESTYLE INTERVENTIONS IN PRE-DIABETICS FOR THE PREVENTION OF Type 2 DIABETES STUDY**

You are invited to be part of an important medical research study

You may be eligible to participate if:

- You are between the ages of 40 and 75 *and*
- Have had a fasting blood sugar level between 100 and 125mg/dL in the last 3 months

The purpose of this research study is to compare an intervention between two groups which may increase adherence to routine lifestyle interventions (diet/exercise) for pre-diabetics in order to prevent the onset of Type 2 Diabetes. Benefits include receiving an individualized lifestyle intervention program. No medications will be used in this study and there will no cost to the participants.

This study is being conducted at the office of David M. Aron, MD at 3180 S. Colima Rd. Hacienda Heights, Ca. For more details on this study or if interested in participating, please notify the receptionist or call Barbara Barlow, ANP at (xxx) xxx-xxxx

APPENDIX D

INFORMED CONSENT

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH (English only)

TITLE OF STUDY

Does home self-monitoring of blood glucose encourage adherence to diet and exercise in pre-diabetic adults as a secondary prevention for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus?

You are asked to participate in a research study conducted by the Principal Investigator, Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP, from the Nursing department at California State University, Long Beach (CSULB). David M. Aron, MD is the medical facility physician and the CSULB faculty advisor is Ahlam Jadalla, RN, MSN, PhD. The results of this study will contribute to the doctoral project of Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP. You were selected as a possible participant in this study because you are between the ages of 40 and 75 and have had a fasting blood sugar of between 100 and 125 mg/dL (pre-diabetic) within the last three months.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to determine whether home self-monitoring of blood glucose levels will encourage pre-diabetic adults to actively participate in their care, resulting in greater adherence to lifestyle modification and a reduction of blood glucose levels in an effort to prevent or delay the onset of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to do the following things:

You will be asked to make an appointment for 2 thirty minute office visits, three months apart, at the office of David M. Aron, MD at 3180 S. Colima Rd., Hacienda Heights, Ca. You will be brought into an exam room and asked to fill out a participant demographics form and short opinion survey on your perceived ability to follow the lifestyle modification program (diet, exercise) offered in this study for the purpose of gathering information that may affect the results of this study. You will receive the same opinion survey in the mail 2 weeks later and be asked to fill it out and return it in the enclosed self-stamped and addressed return envelope. This is for the purpose of validating the survey questions. Your name will not be included on these forms.

You will be given educational material, individually explained by the Principal Investigator, Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP, which will allow you to follow a lifestyle modification program for the purpose of improving your blood sugar levels and preventing the development of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. You will be randomly assigned to one of two groups, the experimental group or the control group by the medical assistant.

The Principal Investigator or medical facility physician will not know which participant has been assigned to each group. There is no other physical time commitment needed from you in this study besides two scheduled office visits.

EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

If you are in the experimental group, you will be given a Freestyle Lite glucometer with test strips and lancets (what you will use to stick your finger, hand, upper arm or thigh with to obtain a small blood sample) with detailed instructions on how to test your blood sugar by the medical assistant. You will also be given a plastic Sharps container, which is used to properly dispose of the used lancets. You will be asked to test your blood sugar once before and once two hours after the first meal of your day every two weeks for three months for a total of 12 tests. Your glucometer will keep a record of your readings for you. You will receive a phone call by the medical assistant at the number you provide, the day before the time you have designated to begin your blood sugar testing, to encourage your efforts in adhering to the lifestyle modification program and as a reminder to perform your blood sugar tests. If you are not available by phone, a message will be left on your answering machine or cell phone. We will not call you or leave any message should you opt not to receive one.

CONTROL GROUP

If you are in the control group, you will also receive a Freestyle Lite glucometer with test strips, lancets, and Sharps disposable container with instruction for your personal use at the end of the three month study period. You will receive a phone call by the medical assistant at the number you have designated, for the purpose of encouraging your efforts in adhering to the lifestyle modification program. If you are not available by phone, a message will be left on your answering machine or cell phone. We will not call you or leave any message should you opt not to receive one.

END OF STUDY

At the end of the three month study period, you will be asked to return to the office for a routine office follow-up and a discussion of all your lab results and vital sign measurements used in this study. You will receive instructions on the proper disposal of the Sharps containers. At this time, all blood sugar readings will be retrieved from the experimental group's glucometers and recorded on the patient questionnaire form by the Medical Assistant. Initial and follow-up lab results of fasting blood sugar, HbA1C, (3 month average of blood sugars) lipids (cholesterol, triglycerides), blood pressure, weight and body mass index measurements will be extracted from your electronic medical record by the researcher, Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP, and recorded on your participant demographics form according to accession and control numbers. There will be no names attached to these forms. A complete result of this study will be made available to you, should you wish to receive it, when available.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

All participants are at risk for breaches of confidentiality which is inherent in all research. If you are in the experimental group, you may experience mild discomfort as a result of performing a total of 12 lancet sticks over 3 months, in order to obtain a small sample of blood needed for the glucose testing. You may experience mild anxiety from an abnormal sugar reading or frustration in performing the blood sugar tests. All participants may feel uncomfortable in changing eating or exercise habits. There is a potential for patients to feel pressured to participate in this study since this research is being conducted at the same facility where the Principal Investigator works.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO SUBJECTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

All participants will receive a glucometer and testing supplies to keep, at no cost to the participant, which may be of benefit in monitoring their blood sugar. Immediate benefits of this study may be the adoption of a healthier diet and exercise pattern with a resulting reduction in blood sugar levels. Longer term benefits may be the prevention or delay of onset of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus which may result in a decrease in associated medical, psychological and financial burdens to the patient, family, community and society.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

There will be no payment to you for your participation in this study nor will there be any additional fees charged to you for any lab tests or office visits associated with this study. All participants will receive, at no charge, a Freestyle Lite Glucometer, test strips, lancets, a Sharps Disposable box, and educational materials as part of a lifestyle modification program. These will be yours to keep. Should you withdraw your participation from this study, at any time, you will still receive these items.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Your name will not be entered on the patient questionnaire or survey tool and all laboratory results and vital sign measurements will be coded by number, not name, on the bottom of the forms. No unauthorized persons will have access to this data. All demographic forms, questionnaires, and laboratory slips will be stored separately from the consent forms within the same locked safe, at the study site for three years with only the Principal Investigator, medical facility physician and faculty advisor having access. Your name and designated phone number will be stored separately in a locked cabinet and used for the sole purpose of reminder calls. Only medical assistants placing these calls will have access to this data. This data will be disposed of (by shredding) immediately after the three month study period. All other forms associated with this study will be disposed of (by shredding) after three years. No data obtained as a direct result from participation in this study will be added to your electronic medical

record. As per routine office procedures, only your vital signs and lab tests which were part of your routine office visits will become part of your electronic medical record. Data retrieved from your electronic medical record for this study will be done only by the Principal Investigator, Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP. The Principal Investigator and medical facility physician will have no knowledge of which participants are in each group.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to be in this study or not. If you volunteer to be in this study, you may withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind and still receive a free Freestyle Lite Glucometer, test strips, lancets with instructions for use as well as educational material for adherence to a lifestyle modification program. Participation or non-participation will not affect your medical care or any other personal consideration or rights you usually expect. You may also refuse to answer any questions you don't want to answer and still remain in the study. The investigator may withdraw you from this research if circumstances arise, which in the opinion of the researcher warrant doing so such as being placed on certain medications or being newly diagnosed with any condition that may affect the results of this study.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact:

Principal Investigator: Barbara Barlow, RN, MSN, ANP at (xxx) xxx-xxxxx

Medical Facility Physician: David M. Aron, MD at (626) 968-0547

Faculty Sponsor: Ahlam Jadalla, RN, MSN, PhD at (562) 850-1536

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH SUBJECTS

You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research subject, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314 or email to research@csulb.edu.

SIGNATURE OF RESEARCH SUBJECT

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form.

Name of Subject

Signature of Subject

Date

Signature of Principal Investigator

Date

APPENDIX E

PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS FORM

DO NOT PUT NAME ON PAPER

1. Age as of last birthday: _____ Today's Date: _____
2. Gender (circle one):
 - a) Male
 - b) Female
3. Marital status (circle one):

a) Married or domestic partner ¹	d) Widowed ⁴
b) Single, never married ²	e) Prefer not to answer ⁵
c) Divorced or separated ³	
4. What ethnicity do you most identify with? (circle one)

a) Caucasian ¹	e) Asian ⁵
b) Hispanic ²	f) Other ⁶ : Specify
c) Middle Eastern ³	g) Prefer not to answer ⁷
d) African American ⁴	
5. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? (circle one)

a) No schooling completed ¹	f) Trade school ⁶
b) Up to 8th grade ²	g) Associate degree ⁷
c) Some high school ³	h) Bachelor's degree ⁸
d) High school graduate or GED ⁴	I) Master's degree or higher ⁹
e) Some college ⁵	j) Prefer not to answer ¹⁰
6. Which best describes your current employment status? (circle one)

a) Employed part-time ¹	f) Military ⁶
b) Employed full time ²	g) Retired ⁷
c) Looking for work ³	h) Unable to work ⁸
d) Student ⁴	I) Prefer not to answer ⁹
e) Homemaker ⁵	
7. Do you or have you ever lived with anyone with diabetes? (circle one)
 - a) Yes¹
 - b) No²
 - c) Prefer not to answer³

8. How would you characterize your level of physical activity at this time? (*circle one*)

(Note: Baseline activity refers to light intensity activities of daily living such as standing, walking slowly, and lifting lightweight objects.)

- a) Inactive (no activity beyond baseline)¹
 - b) Low (activity beyond baseline but fewer than 150 minutes or 2½ hours a week)²
 - c) Medium (150 minutes or 2½ hours to 300 minutes or 5 hours a week)³
 - d) High (more than 300 minutes or 5 hours per week)⁴
9. Have you ever been told that you are pre-diabetic or have a higher than normal fasting blood sugar? (*circle one*)
- a) Yes¹
 - b) No²

APPENDIX F

PREDIABETIC SELF-EFFICACY QUESTIONNAIRE

CONTROL # _____ -01 DATE _____

Please tell us *how confident* you feel in performing certain activities. For each of the following questions, please circle the number that best corresponds to how confident you feel about being able to do the task regularly at the present time.

		Not at all confident	Somewhat confident	Neither confident nor unconfident	Very confident	Totally confident
1	How confident are you that you can adhere to a low carbohydrate diet?	1	2	3	4	5
2	How confident are you that you can achieve a healthier weight?	1	2	3	4	5
3	How confident are you that you can monitor your blood sugar?	1	2	3	4	5
4	How confident are you that you can control your blood sugar?	1	2	3	4	5
5	How confident are you that you can prevent or delay the onset of diabetes?	1	2	3	4	5
6	How confident are you that you can achieve a healthier lifestyle?	1	2	3	4	5
7	How confident are you that you can increase your physical activity level?	1	2	3	4	5

Adapted from "Self-efficacy and Health Behaviors Toward the Prevention of Diabetes Among High Risk Individuals Living in Appalachia," by E. Serrano, J. Leiferman, and S. Dauber, 2007, *Journal of Community Health*, 32, 121–135, doi:10.1007/s10900-006-9034-4

APPENDIX G

MEDICAL ASSISTANT SCRIPTED PHONE REMINDER

“Hello, my name is _____, and I am calling you from the office of Dr. David M. Aron, and Barbara Barlow, Nurse Practitioner. I am calling you regarding your ongoing participation in the study, Does Home Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose Encourage Adherence to Diet and Exercise in Prediabetic Adults as a Secondary Prevention for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus?

“I would just like to encourage you to continue your lifestyle modification program and remind you that if you have any questions, to feel free to contact either Barbara Barlow ANP, the Principal Investigator, or Dr. David M. Aron, the Co-Investigator at (626) 968-0547.”

Experimental Group

Those in the experimental group will receive the above message with the following additional reminder at the end of the above message:

“I would also like to remind you that tomorrow is the day you designated to perform your blood glucose test. Please remember to test once before breakfast and to test once more 2 hours after breakfast. Your machine will automatically record your results. Thank you and goodbye.”

APPENDIX H

FREESTYLE LITE® PACKAGE

APPENDIX I
CODING TOOL

Coding Tool

CONTROL #- _____ **Serial #-** _____

Baseline FBS _____ Date _____

Baseline HbA1c _____ Date _____

Baseline Weight _____ Date _____

Baseline BMI _____ Date _____

Baseline Total chol _____ HDL-C _____, LDL-C _____ Trig _____ Date _____

Follow-up FBS _____ Date _____

Follow-up HbA1c _____ Date _____

Follow-up Weight _____ Date _____

Follow-up BMI _____ Date _____

Follow-up Total chol _____ HDL-C _____, LDL-C _____ Trig _____ Date _____

GLUCOMETER TESTS (fasting - odd number lines, after meal -even number lines)

1. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 7. _____ Date _____ Time _____

2. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 8. _____ Date _____ Time _____

3. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 9. _____ Date _____ Time _____

4. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 10. _____ Date _____ Time _____

5. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 11. _____ Date _____ Time _____

6. _____ Date _____ Time _____ 12. _____ Date _____ Time _____

APPENDIX J

CALORIEKING®

Compliments of
SANOFI

2012
EDITION

THE CALORIEKING®
**Calorie
FAT &**
**Carbohydrate
Counter**

ALLAN BORUSHEK
-DIETITIAN-
"THE CALORIE KING"

**Includes
200
Fast-Food
Chains**

**Plus
SODIUM
& ALCOHOL
COUNTERS**

**Bonus
DIABETES
DIET GUIDE**
IN ASSOCIATION WITH
Joslin
Diabetes
Center

FOOD PRODUCT UPDATES ~ www.CalorieKing.com

APPENDIX K

PREDIABETES INFORMATION SHEET

WHAT IS PREDIABETES AND WHY SHOULD WE CARE ABOUT IT?

Pre-diabetes is a condition that almost always precedes Type 2 diabetes and is identified by a laboratory fasting blood glucose level that is higher than normal but not high enough to be diagnosed as diabetes.

Current research suggests that damage to the blood vessels in the body may already be occurring during pre-diabetes. People with pre-diabetes often have no symptoms but are more likely to develop Type 2 diabetes over time. Having Type 2 diabetes increases your risk for many serious health problems which can affect your heart, eyes, nerves, skin, kidneys and more. People with Type 2 diabetes have a higher risk of dying from heart disease or stroke.

WHAT IS THE GOOD NEWS FOR PREDIABETICS?

The good news is that you can prevent or delay the onset of Type 2 diabetes by adopting a healthier lifestyle through diet and exercise. Genetics play a role in developing Type 2 diabetes, but so do lifestyle factors. You cannot change your genetics BUT you can change your lifestyle to include better eating and exercise habits.

HOW DO I LOWER MY RISK FOR DEVELOPING TYPE 2 DIABETES?

In today's busy times, there is a need to offer people simple tips so that they can make healthier lifestyle changes with minimal effort. In general, maintaining a healthy weight through a reduction of "sugars or carbs" in the diet is a first step towards maintaining good glucose control. Increased physical activity such as increased walking or simply "moving around" can also help to maintain your blood glucose levels.

APPENDIX L

LOW-CARB HANDOUT

How many carbs are in my favorite foods?

For foods that come in packages, the best place to find the carb count is on the Nutrition Facts label. The grams of total carbohydrate on the label are the key to carb counting. Don't worry about counting the sugar and fiber grams. They are included in the total carb number.

Check serving size. Information on the label is based on the serving size

See how many grams of carb are in each serving

Decide whether the food fits into your meal plan

Nutrition Facts

Serving Size 1 cup (40g)	
Servings Per Container 2.5	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 150	Calories From Fat 10
% Daily Value*	
Total Fat 3g	4%
Saturated Fat 0.5g	2%
Trans Fat 0g	0%
Cholesterol 0mg	0%
Sodium 10mg	1%
Total Carbohydrate 24g	9%
Dietary Fiber 4g	15%
Sugars 1g	
Protein 5g	
Vitamin A	4%
Vitamin C	2%
Calcium	20%
Iron	4%

* Percent Daily Values are based on a 2,000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calorie needs.

Carb counting is important to maintain a healthy blood sugar. Remember these important points:

- Foods containing the most carbs are bread, cereals, grains, rice, pasta, potatoes, beans corn, carrots, all fruits and fruit juices and "sweets".
- Food groups that generally do not contain carbs are meats, eggs, cheese and fats.
- A sensible low carb diet has a total of between 100 and 120 grams of carbs a day. Spread this out over 3 meals a day (For example, 30-40 grams of carbs per meal).
- We recommend 30 grams per meal for women and 40 grams per meal for men. A sensible snack food should contain 15 grams of carbs or less.
- Portion size is critical to maintain a healthy weight and also to allow you to incorporate the foods you like into your diet. Know your portion sizes, even if you have to weigh or measure your foods. **EAT SLOWLY AND NEVER ALLOW YOURSELF TO FEEL FULL AFTER EATING!!!**

APPENDIX M

PHYSIOLOGY OF EATING

PRINTED BY LILLY DIABETES FOR USE IN THE EDUCATION OF PATIENTS

Personal solutions for everyday life.

Barbara Barlow, ANP

WHAT HAPPENS WHEN YOU EAT? (NON-DIABETIC)

- Some of the food in your stomach breaks down into sugars - one of which is glucose, the body's main fuel.
- Sugar enters your bloodstream and the level of sugar in your blood begins to rise.
- When your body senses an increase in sugar, it sends a signal to your pancreas.
- The pancreas makes insulin and releases it into the bloodstream.
- Insulin lowers the level of blood sugar by acting as a key to unlock your body's cells and allows sugar to pass from the bloodstream into your cells.
- The level of sugar in your bloodstream falls as the sugar passes into your cells.
- Your cells use the sugar for fuel.

Legend:
 ◆ Insulin in the blood
 ◆ Sugar in the blood
 ▲ Sugar in the cell
 ● Food

Notes

GET SMART ABOUT CARBS

Carbohydrates, or carbs, are the fiber, sugar, and starch in the foods you eat. How much different foods raise your blood sugar depends on how many carbs and the types of carbs they contain.

<p>Low (0-15g)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pretzels (1 cup, 40g) • Cooked Pasta (1 cup, 39g) • Fat-free frozen yogurt (1 cup, 39g) 	
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Source: American Diabetes Association, MyFoodAdvisor™ tool

CONVENIENT WAYS TO KEEP ACTIVE

Make sure you get daily physical activity.

- Take the stairs instead of the elevator
- Park your car at the far end of the parking lot
- Take regular walks
- Work in the yard or garden
- Take an exercise class

Remember to check with your healthcare team before beginning an exercise routine.

Source: American Diabetes Association

APPENDIX N

GLUCOMETER INSTRUCTIONS

glucometer

lancing device

test strip vial

test strip

lancet

- The FreeStyle Lite System has an operating range of 40° to 104° F (4° to 40° C).
- Store the test strip package in a cool, dry place between 40° and 86° F (4° to 30° C).
- Use test strips only within the system operating temperature range.
- Keep away from direct sunlight and heat.

Using the Lancet Device

- Snap off cap on lancing device at an angle.
- Insert lancet firmly into the white lancet holder cup.
- Twist off rounded top and replace cap.
- Set the lancing level (Level 1 is most shallow).
- Pull dark cocking handle out until it clicks in place.
- Select testing site and lightly touch device to skin. (Avoid lancing areas with obvious veins or moles)
- Press the release button. Apply blood drop onto one side of test strip.
- After finishing testing, remove lancet from device. (Pinch the white clip that holds the lancet)
- Discard your used lancet into your Sharp's container.

Performing a Blood Glucose Test

- #### Prepare Your Meter

Insert a FreeStyle Lite Test Strip into the meter until it stops. The meter will power on.

Note: If you do not start the test within two minutes, the meter will turn off. To restart your meter, take out the unused FreeStyle Lite Test Strip and reinsert it into the meter.

System Check

System Check Screen

When the meter powers on, this screen will appear so that you can make sure the display is working properly.

Blood Drop and Test Strip Symbols

The Blood Drop and Test Strip symbols will appear on the display screen. Your meter is now ready to apply blood sample.

Important: The FreeStyle Lite Meter should only be used with FreeStyle Lite Test Strips. Using other test strips with this meter can produce inaccurate results.
- #### Obtain a Blood Sample

Select a test site. There are differences in testing on fingers versus other alternative sites. Use your lancing device to obtain a blood sample. Refer to the Lancing Device insert for detailed instructions on how to use the FreeStyle Lancing Device.

Important: Use only one sample area of the test strip per test. Do not apply blood to both sample areas. Test strips may be used only once. Discard used test strips. You can continue to fill the test strip for up to 60 seconds. Be sure to reapply the sample to the same sample area.

Test Strip Sample Area
- #### Fill the FreeStyle Lite Test Strip with Blood

 - Make sure that the FreeStyle Lite Test Strip is in the meter and the meter is powered on. (If the meter is off, take out the test strip and reinsert it into the meter.) You are now ready to apply the blood sample.
 - Bring the FreeStyle Lite Test Strip to the blood sample at a slight angle.
 - The FreeStyle Lite Test Strip acts like a sponge and pulls the blood into the strip through the sample area.

Test Strip Sample Area

APPENDIX O**SHARPS CONTAINER DISPOSAL INSTRUCTIONS****Instructions For Proper Disposal of Sharps Container**

The Sharps container you have received, as a participant in this study for the purpose of disposing of your used lancets is considered a household hazardous waste and needs to be disposed of in a proper manner. Never put a Sharps container in a trash or recycling bin.

We encourage you to bring your Sharps container to our medical facility for proper disposal:

**David M. Aron, MD
3180 S. Colima Rd Suite A
Hacienda Heights, Ca 91745**

The County of Los Angeles offers a Household Hazardous and Electronic Waste Collection Program where you can also dispose of your Sharps container. They have permanent centers in various locations and also mobile collection events. For more information call 1 (888) CLEAN LA or www.888CleanLA.com

For information about Sharps and lancing devices, you can visit the FDA's website:

<http://www.fda.gov/diabetes/lancing.html>